

**A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON THE PERSPECTIVES OF TEACHERS
AND STUDENTS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF
BAREWALL CLASSROOM POLICY**

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A Comparative Analysis on the Perspectives of Teachers and Students in the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

Trixie M. Villanueva,* Evelyn G. Erellana
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to explore the experiences of teachers and students regarding the implementation of the barewall classroom policy and identify the challenges and coping mechanisms involved. A qualitative research approach using a phenomenological method, specifically comparative analysis, was employed. The participants comprised ten bona fide high school teachers and ten bona fide high school students from Sagayan National High School. Findings revealed that both teachers and students had to adapt to the changes brought by the policy. The barewall classroom policy was found to enhance students' focus, although students relying on visual stimulation had difficulty adapting. Based on their experiences, the participants highlighted the necessity of embracing changes, removing classroom decorations, and carefully considering classroom design. They emphasized the importance of community involvement, technology integration, clear communication, and creating a conducive learning space. The study participants stressed the value of cooperation, maintaining classroom cleanliness, and better concentration. They noted benefits for students, teachers' personality development, and the positive impact of the barewall policy on the teaching-learning process. The study reflects on elicitation techniques, suggesting future operationalization. The research underscores the need for flexibility and understanding in implementing the barewall classroom policy, highlighting its benefits and challenges.

Keywords: *barewall classroom policy, teachers, students, comparative analysis, Philippines*

Introduction

A typical traditional classroom has no design but as the years passes, this become a notion that needs to be solved. Classroom design plays a vital part on students' learning outcomes. Classroom design encompasses a huge range of elements that contribute to creating a conducive learning environment. A classroom with no wall decorations, or bare walls, differs significantly with the Department of Education's emphasis on the need of carefully designed learning spaces. (Rashid, 2023).

In Nigeria, one of the major concerns of having no decoration in the classroom is the cultural perception of the classroom environment where decorations are often seen as a vital for creating and engaging and motivating learning environment. Additionally, many Nigerian schools face resource constraints, making it difficult to provide adequate training for teachers on how to implement a minimalist approach effectively. Moreover, absence of decorations could also lead to feelings of alienation among students, as a sense of belonging is often reinforced by personal and culturally relevant elements in the classroom (Akenyemi, 2021).

In the Philippines, students perceive the classroom as important for personal expression engagement. Lack of resources in underfunded schools complicates the transition as teachers may not receive the necessary training or support to adapt to a minimalist environment. Misinterpretation of the policy could lead to the assumption that a bare environment lacks educational material, which disengage students who thrive in more personalized paces (UNESCO, 2020).

With the factors mentioned, a study should be conducted. Thus, a study highlighting the perspectives of teachers and students in the implementation of barewall classroom policy is needed. More essentially, the study holds immense social relevance as this will set out a greater understanding with regards to the perspectives of teachers and students on the bare wall classroom policy. With, this study will offer a better understanding on how teachers and students will adjust to the effects of bare wall classroom policy in the teaching and learning process.

There were several studies that had been conducted in related research endeavor. For instance, Sabatini (2021)'s "The Correlation Between Students' Perceptions of Classroom Environment and their English Achievement of Eight Grade Students' of SMP IT IQRA Bengkulu" study was conducted to determine the effect of classroom environment on English achievement. On the other hand, the study Wali et al., (2019)' s study entitled "Impact of Classroom Environment on Student's Performance in Language", determined the impact of classroom environment on the academic performance. In addition, the study of Woo et al., (2022) entitled "Student's Perception of the Classroom Environment: A Comparison between Innovative and Traditional Classrooms", sought to examine the level of interactivity in traditional and innovative classroom and to know the perception of physical classroom features affect the level of attitude toward the classroom environment. In this study, it aims to explore the viewpoints of students and teachers on the classroom environment, specifically focusing on the effects of bare-wall classrooms. It will investigate how this policy can potentially enhance the teaching and learning processes for both educators and students.

In this study, the dissemination of research findings will involve distributing copies of research papers, reports, or concise summaries to pertinent stakeholders, collaborators, and community members. This dissemination strategy is designed to enhance accessibility for

key individuals, empowering them to engage actively with the significant findings of the study. Through the provision of research papers, the researcher seeks to amplify the impact and relevance of the study across academic, collaborative, and community spheres. Consideration should also be given to publishing and presenting the research to further extend its reach and influence.

Research Questions

The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore the experiences, challenges, and insights of teachers and students at Sagayen National High School in relation to the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy. Specifically, the study aims to gather data on the motivations of teachers and students, as well as their strategies for coping with difficulties and struggles arising from this policy. Additionally, the research seeks to comprehensively understand the perspectives of teachers and students on the bare wall classroom policy, with the goal of assisting them in overcoming the challenges they encounter. Utilizing an inductive approach, this study will employ qualitative methods such as interviews to delve deeply into the viewpoints of participants, capturing the essence and entirety of their perspectives on the policy. Specifically, it sought to answer:

1. What are the experiences of teachers and students with regards to the implementation of bare wall classroom policy?
2. How do the teachers and students overcome such challenges with regards to the implementation of bare wall classroom policy?
3. What are the insights of the teachers and students with regards to the implementation of bare wall classroom policy?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative approach specifically phenomenology approach, which entails gathering and examining non-numerical data to comprehend ideas, viewpoints, or experiences. It might be utilized to discover intricate details of an issue or come up with fresh concepts. Qualitative research is an approach that takes place in natural settings and is not guided by pre-existing theories. The collected data was analyzed for its meaning and context and was presented in a descriptive manner without the use of numerical data. The main emphasis was on understanding the dynamics and processes that occur within the field of study (Universitas Medan Area, 2020).

In this study, qualitative approach was the most appropriate approach for this study because of its data collection process which was through gathering subjective experiences from the participants and the way how the data was interpreted. Since this study was focused on the experiences and challenges of students on the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy, this qualitative research design would allow the researcher to gather significant information from the participant's point of view which is very crucial for this study.

Meanwhile, various methods were used in this phenomenological research, such as group discussions to explore ideas and behaviors and in-depth interviews to gain insight into personal experiences, and examination of written materials such as official documents, news articles, and personal journals to gain knowledge about both public and private perspectives (Hammarberg et al., 2016). Additionally, qualitative research design provides researchers with a valuable benefit as the use of phenomenological research method would allow the researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of their subject-matter, which cannot be attained easily through surveys that use only closed-ended questions. Qualitative techniques provide a flexible and dynamic approach to research, as it allows the researcher to delve deeper into responses given by participants and explore the subject matter in more depth during the research process. In contrast to a structured survey where this level of engagement is not possible (Tiley, 2017).

In this study, the researcher utilized qualitative research techniques, specifically in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, which explores the lived experiences of participants in relation to the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy. By engaging in these methods, the researcher aims to uncover the nuanced perspectives and insights of individuals regarding the policy. The qualitative research design was facilitated the gathering of diverse and relevant information from participants, acknowledging their varying experiences and challenges. Through phenomenological inquiry, the researcher sought to understand the essence of how individuals perceive and make sense of the bare wall classroom policy, delving into the subjective meanings and interpretations that shape their experiences. This approach provided a deeper understanding of the participants' perspectives and contribute to a rich and detailed exploration of the topic.

Participants

In this phenomenological study, the key participants were the students and teachers of Sagayen National High School. The selection of participants was justified because the intended participants are high school teachers and high school students. Thus, they were the only ones who can provide authentic accounts about the research topic. Twenty participants in which ten (10) teachers and ten (10) students were carefully selected in this research endeavor. Ten (10) of have been subjected to in-depth interviews in which five (5) teachers and five (5) students wherein each of them was interviewed individually by the researcher through face-to-face interview. Meanwhile, five (5) students and five (5) participated in the focus group discussion (FGD) wherein all of them were interviewed on the face-to-face interview to which they discussed what the researcher has presented to them.

Better data was obtained through a qualitative research study with fewer participants. A smaller group made it simpler for the researcher to establish deep bonds with the participants, which results in more organic conversations and superior data (Crouch & Mackenzie,

2006).

Upon participant selection, purposive sampling was used to ensure that only those who can give the necessary data would be able to participate in my study. Purposive sampling was applied which highly rely on a set of inclusion criteria. This sampling method was non-probability type of sampling which guarantees the acquisition of authentic lived experiences. This would guarantee as the sampling method employed participants who were closely immersed or involved in the phenomenon being investigated (Ellis, 2016).

In the recruitment process, the researcher religiously followed the inclusion criteria. Firstly, each participant must be a student and a teacher of Sagayan National High School. Secondly, the participant must be 18 years above who is a full-time student and a full-time teacher. Lastly, this was applicable across all year levels and programs if they possessed the above-mentioned criteria.

Procedure

The researcher employed different steps in data collection as well as gathering relevant information for the study. In collecting the data, the researcher undergone several steps and measures which were specified below. This was to be made sure that the findings of this study would gain ethical soundness and a high extent of trustworthiness.

First, the researcher submitted her manuscript for it to be checked by the research technical panel. Afterwards, the researcher wrote a permission letter addressed to the institution where she conducted her study. After writing the permission letter, the researcher went personally go to the school where she conducted her study. The researcher secured the signature of her research adviser as well as the signature of the research director before going to the Department of Education. Afterwards, she identified her research participants using the purposive sampling technique.

On another note, the participants were selected based on the following criteria: (1) each participant must be a student of Sagayan National High School; (2) the participant must be 18 years old and above who is a full-time student and a full-time teacher; (3) this is applicable across all year levels and programs if they possessed the above-mentioned criteria.

Second, the participants were asked to read and understand first the consent and agreement form that was handed out by the researcher before they can sign it. This was to ensure that the participants were willing to share their knowledge and experiences to the researcher for the completion of the study.

Third, the participants were oriented about the study. The orientation included the purpose of the interview, information regarding the confidentiality of the data that they gave, as well as the benefits that they gained in cooperating in this study.

Fourth, in interviewing, the researcher recorded their conversation with the participants in a face-to-face interview. Afterwards, the researcher transcribed the collected information before translating it from raw language to standard English language. After translating that data, the researcher identified the themes as well as the principles of thematic analysis. Finally, the researcher seeks for assistance of a data analyst through handing out the themes that has been identified for analyzation.

Data Analysis

In this research study, the data gathered was presented and analyzed based on the needs and objectives of the research endeavor. To generate the findings of the study, sufficient analysis of the content of the participants' responses was done. Thus, the goal of data analysis was to find for common patterns that will disclose ideas which may answer the research questions being established in this study.

Performing a systematic search and organization of interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual materials were referred to as qualitative data analysis, according to Lune and Beng (2017). This procedure was carried out to give the researcher the opportunity to gather information and to improve public comprehension of the phenomenon or research issue.

The replies from the participants in this study were collected, transcribed, and then was translated from their original languages into Standard English. The primary source of data for this study's data analysis were the transcripts. To extract the study's conclusions, the data undergone several treatments and processing steps.

The next step for the researcher was a qualitative topic analysis. One of the most popular types of analysis which is reading over a data set, such as the transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups and looking for patterns in meaning to extract themes. Thematic analysis involved an active reflexive process in which the researcher's personal experience was crucial to extracting meaning from the data. When seeing trends in data, learning about qualitative analysis, and incorporating research subjects in the analysis process, thematic analysis should be taken into consideration (Delve, 2020). In this study, the researcher categorized the themes for analysis. She looked for the similarities put of the ideas or codes that were derived after the codification process. At this point, major themes were produced. These themes were utilized to give shape to the general description of the phenomenon being studied. The themes that emerged from the study was discussed and was elaborated thoroughly to provide a vivid description hence, the researcher can draw the conclusion and verification.

Finally, data reduction was used in analyzing the data. This means that this employed of deleting unnecessary data and modifying them into a useful material for the sake of the study. This was for the purpose of making the data comprehensible to the readers (Sutton &

Austin, 2015).

The researcher purified the data and removed the information or samples which do not carry much information essential on the inquiry at hand.

Ethical Considerations

Individuals who were the high school teachers and high school students in general were the study's major focus. To maintain their trust in us, the researcher guaranteed their safety and provide them with complete protection. The researcher also adhered to the following ethical principles when conducting research: respect for individuals, goodness, fairness, consent, and secrecy (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons was the researcher's obligation to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants. Self-sufficiency must be avoided to maintain trust, friendship, and confidence among participants and the researcher. Prior to the administration of interviews, the researcher would ask permission from the parents and the participants itself and she must adjust upon their availability. Therefore, she must set the interview schedule ahead of time. This was done to ensure that the researcher would not be a reason that her participants may have to absent from their respective classes; also, to avoid delay or cancellation of their important errands.

Before gathering of data, the researcher contacted first her participants regarding her study. She informed them about her research, and she made sure they were willing to share their experiences with her. The researcher also informed them that she would record the whole conversation. However, she would not proceed with the interview right after receiving their agreement. Since her participants were teachers and students, she presumed that they were busy with their studies. Hence, to avoid any conflicts with their time, the researcher asked them when they were vacant for her to set a specific date and time for the interview.

Moreover, the researcher certainly made sure that the participants would not be harm physically and psychologically in her study. Also, she must make it certain that she would refer to her panel of examinees with regards to all the steps that she would take prior to the conduct of her study to have an appropriate procedure of collecting the data. Furthermore, the researcher would hereby disclose that her participants were in no way vulnerable to coercion or any sort of exploitation by the principal investigator. Respect shall be highly acknowledged.

Benevolence requires commitment to minimize participant risks rather than maximizing gains owing to them. To protect each participant from risk, the interviewee's anonymity must be maintained. Participants would always be protected, and no information file would ever be unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

This study made sure that the participants would have their own share of benefits as these would generate insights and coping mechanisms that can be useful in improving the relationship teachers and students in general. Participants would be able to share their experiences and challenges at the same time they could be able to learn how others cope up with their challenges. In addition, the researcher ensured that her participants would not be exposed in any risk during the conduct of this study. Since pandemic was over, the researcher conducted a face-to-face interview in this study.

Consent is another way to show respect to the informants within the research. This is to make all the participants aware of what are the objectives and purpose of the research that they are going to involve. Written consent was given to them that certifies their approval. After they approved, they can participate the in-depth interviews and the focus group discussion. Of course, they would be informed on the results and findings of the study (Creswell, 2012).

Before conducting this study, the researcher made sure that her participants were willing to share their experiences. She informed them with the benefits they could gain in participating in this study as well as how they would be able to contribute for the improvement of the life of the teachers and students. She provided an information sheet for the participants to be aware that they have the rights to refuse to answer sensitive questions her, rights to ask questions, rights to leave the interview without any explanation and to make sure that the participation is voluntary. After their approval, the researcher informed them right away regarding the information they if it should be treated with confidentiality. She would give them a consent forms for their participation and for the recording that they would sign to give their consent. Lastly, the researcher informed the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the study result.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques was used. Meaning, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and were shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others were eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

By keeping their identities hidden and maintaining their confidentiality, the researcher-built trust with the participants in this study. Being anonymous and maintaining privacy may help keep the respondent safe and comfortable within the bounds of the law, like when she interviewed the teachers and students about their experiences and challenges on the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy. Although there were participants that were contented with their details being transcribed, the final report and transcripts were not included such as the subjects' names or other identifying information. To protect the participant's privacy, the researcher would destroy the recorded discussion once the study will be over and written report is available. After the transcription, she saved the audio file in a secure location.

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the respondents should be highlighted as they become an integral part of the success of this study. It is recommended that respondents should be given due credits in all their participation extended in our research. Also, the researcher gave them souvenirs as a sign of their gratitude to their efforts on the study. The researcher would hope that through this study, they would be set free into whatever negative experiences they have as a teacher and a student especially in this situation and maintain a good bearing into what positive contributions they could offer in this study (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

Since the researcher would identify her participants through purposive sampling technique, she can guarantee that the participants were equitably chosen. Hence, there would be no occurrence of such situations wherein the participants were dismissing from participating in the study just because of their personal classification (age, gender, sex, ethnicity, etc.) even though they were qualified.

During the interview, the researcher always made sure that the participants would be comfortable and safe all throughout the conversation. She always treated them with fairness and respect to avoid partiality. She also ensured that only their relevant and accurate responses would be reflected in her study. As a form of gratitude, she would give sensible tokens to all her participants regarding their experiences as students on the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy which were very crucial for the accomplishment of this study.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts. Part one tackles the participants' data, from which the qualitative data was collected. Part two covers the data analysis procedures and the steps in categorizing the emergent themes from in-depth interviews and focus group discussion results. Part three deals with the response to the interview and FGD questions under each research problem and part four contains the summary of the responses.

The participants in my study were the students and teachers of Sagayan National High School. As illustrated in Table 1, there were twenty (20) people involved in this study: ten (10) for the focus group discussion and ten (10) for the in-depth interviews; and among the twenty (20), ten (10) were students and ten (10) were teachers.

Participants

In-depth Interview. There were ten key informants in this study; five were students and five were teachers. Following the principle of confidentiality, each participant for the in-depth interview was assigned a pseudonym during the conduct of the interview as used by Bernal (2014), which assignment was made according to their unique physical characteristics and attitudes shown during the interview sessions. For instance, Forehead was a name given to the informant who has a mannerism of holding her forehead when answering the questions, while Eyes was given to the informant who keeps on blinking his eyes in answering the questions during the interview. One of the participants was named Shoulders because when she answers every question, she keeps on shrugging her shoulders. Moreover, Hands was also the name given to the informant who always claps her hands while he answers my questions in a well detailed manner during the interview session, while Hair was the name given to the informant who always touch her hair in answering the questions in during the interview session. In addition, Thumb was name given to the informant who always used a thumbs up when answering the questions during the interview session, while Elbow was name given to the informant who always touches his elbow in when he answers the questions directly during the interview session. Finger was name given to the informant who always touch her flinch her fingers in giving her answers during the interview session, while Palm was name given to the informant who always raise his palm in giving her answers during the interview session, and lastly, Nails was name given to the informant who always pinch her fingers in answering the questions during the interview session.

Focus Group. In the same manner, ten participants in the focus group discussion were also given pseudonyms. The participants were named Nose, Eyebrows, Ears, Cheeks, Chin, Mouth, Head, Leg, Belly and Hair. Nose was name given to the participant who keeps on touching his nose in giving his answers during the interview session. Eyebrows was name given to the participant who raises her eyebrows in giving her answers during the discussion. Ears was also the name given to the participant who shows her full attention in giving her answers during the in discussion. Cheeks was name given to the participant whose cheeks became red in giving her answers during the discussion. Chin was a name given to the participant who keeps on holding his chin in giving his answer during the discussion. Then, Mouth was name given to the participant who emphasized his answered through the movements of his mouth in giving his answers during the discussion. Head was a name given to the participant who keeps on nodding in giving his answers during the discussion. Leg was also a name given to the participant who always moves her legs in giving her answers during the discussion. Belly was given to the participant who touches her belly in giving her answers during the discussion. Lastly, Hair was a name given to the participant who keeps on touching her hair in giving her answers during the discussion.

There are different set of questions given to the students and teachers. The participants were based on the set criteria stated in the previous chapter of this study. The interview sessions that the researcher had with the participants manifested the composition of the sumptuous information included in this study.

The in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted through face-to-face. The researcher used smart phones to record the data given by the participants for the recording of data is a very important factor for the validity and credibility.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Course</i>	<i>Code</i>
Forehead	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	IDI- S1
Eyes	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	IDI-S2
Shoulders	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	IDI- S3
Hands	18	Male	Grade 12	STEM	IDI-S4
Nails	18	Male	Grade 12	STEM	IDI-S5
<i>In-depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>		<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Code</i>
Thumb	38	Female		15	IDI- T1
Elbow	40	Male		13	IDI-T 2
Finger	35	Female		8	IDI- T 3
Palm	30	Male		7	IDI-T 4
Nails	29	Female		6	IDI-T 5
Total = 10					
<i>Focus Group Discussions (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Course</i>	<i>Code</i>
Nose	18	Male	Grade 12	STEM	FGD- S1
Eyebrows	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	FGD-S2
Ears	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	FGD- S3
Cheeks	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	FGD- S4
Chin	18	Female	Grade 12	STEM	FGD-S5
<i>Focus Group Discussions (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>		<i>Years in Service</i>	<i>Code</i>
Mouth	42	Male		15	FGD- T1
Head	34	Male		6	FGD-T2
Leg	35	Female		9	FGD- T3
Belly	39	Female		10	FGD-T4
Hair	40	Female		9	FGD-T5
Total = 10					

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, the audio recordings were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis began with the coding process. Coding is the process of organizing the materials into portions of segments of the texts before bringing meaning to the information. The coding process describes the people’s settings and categories of themes for analysis. These themes were used to shape a general description of the phenomenon being studied. The data results were presented in the form of table. This data gathered was handed to the assigned data analyst to approve and verify the data and the emerging themes that the researcher had made and analyzed.

The themes were presented per research question to categorize this data and are referred to as central themes. The themes that emerged from the study were thoroughly discussed to provide a vivid description. Adjacent to the major themes in the table were the core ideas of the participants’ responses.

The second step was the data analysis, which we settled on as presented in Table 2. To categorize this data, the themes were presented by research question and referred to as central themes. The other significant themes in the table were the co-ideas from the participants’ responses. Another column was included in the table showing the frequency of the responses, which became the basis for the classification of general, typical, and variant, as discussed above.

Research Question 1: What are the experiences of teachers and students with regards to the implementation of the barewall classroom policy?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with the participants. Several sub-questions were asked to elicit their concept with regards to the issues of academic honesty and distance learning.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2 and Table 3. From the answers of the informants and participant, 8 major themes emerged: valuing less distraction, stressing the importance of visual stimulation, adhering to classroom changes, enhancing student focus, following the removal of decorations, enhancing student focus, viewing the importance of planning and preparation, and doing careful consideration.

Valuing Less Distraction

The barewall classroom policy values less distraction to help students focus better. By keeping the environment simple and minimal, it reduces visual clutter. This allows students to engage more with their lessons. A clean and organized space can lead to improved

learning. Overall, a minimalist approach supports better concentration in the classroom.

Table 2. Experiences of Students with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

Emerging Themes	Supporting Statements
Valuing Less Distraction	<p>“So, it was made to be less distracting for us who are in higher grades, but for elementary level students, it might be less engaging for them to enter school because usually back then when we were in elementary, going to school was fun because the teacher would prepare various things on the wall, and you would have fun.” (IDI S1)</p> <p>“I can say that this barewall classroom policy is nice since the classroom looks cozy. By implementing this policy, it lessens the distraction of the students since many would look at the design and do not give attention to their classes.” (FGD S5)</p> <p>“The classroom looks plain and boring because it is not interesting to look at when you enter the classroom because yes, it is just bland to look at, but well, it was less distraction now.” (FGD S2)</p> <p>“For me, there is no problem with the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy. I feel more refreshed in my surroundings when there are no distractions in my line of sight. However, I believe the impact is greater on students who can learn through the designs in their surroundings.” (FGD S3)</p>
Importance of Visual Stimulation	<p>“The challenge for me in our classroom is that it is not as attractive to me as the classroom we have now. It is just too plain for us. It is okay for us, but not very aesthetically pleasing. For me, the classroom is not as visually appealing as I would like it to be.” (IDI S1)</p> <p>“For me, the challenges I have faced is that I was not able to get any ideas when our teacher will give us a task or an essay task because I do not see any quotes or designs which I can base my essay on. So, for me that was the challenge.” (IDI S5)</p> <p>“For me, I am no longer motivated because I can no longer read the writings on the walls like, “Honesty is the best policy.” (FGD S1)</p> <p>“The challenges I have encountered are that it seems too plain in my perspective, so it feels like nothing really enters my mind when the teacher discusses.” (FGD S2)</p> <p>“For me, it is easy to learn if I have something to see in my surroundings because it motivates me, but I was surprised, and it took me a while to adjust since I was used to having designs in our classroom before.” (FGD S4)</p>
Adhering to Classroom Changes	<p>“I was surprised by everyone because before, when I entered the classroom, I used to enjoy looking at the colorful decorations, but now it is just simple.” (IDI S3)</p> <p>“So, as senior high students, having a plain or bare wall in our classroom it does not really affect me because I am not very interested in the design of our classroom. We focus on our studies, on how to excel in school. Back then, when there was still a design, you could also learn a bit from the quotes and pictures they displayed. Especially in elementary, you could recognize who Rizal is, who Bonifacio is, things like that. The negative side, perhaps, is that when that is taken away, you lose those trivia or facts that you could learn.” (IDI S1)</p> <p>“At first, I was shocked on why DEPED would implement this kind of policy because for me, it really helps and I had long time moving on because I do really learn through visual representations so, now that the classroom is plain, I just let myself adapt the policy because I have nothing to do with it.” (IDI S5)</p> <p>“Actually, I was really used to having designs in our classroom because since elementary school, there were always designs, so I was surprised when our teacher said that our classroom would be like this now, that is why I also had to adjust.” (FGD S3)</p>
Enhances Students Focus	<p>“The impact is more on the positive side for me because, yes, it is true that it is less distracting and not too cluttered when you look around. It is not messy to look at. So, you can focus on studying. They say that once they see your classroom with bare walls, it looks nice to see, since they also say that when your environment is clean, you can study well.” (IDI S1)</p> <p>“As a student, the impact of the barewall policy is that we can focus a bit more easily since the surroundings have a plain and simple design.” (IDI S3)</p> <p>“Just like I mentioned repeatedly, as a student, it really brings a positive impact on me because we are more focused on the teacher’s discussion and less distracted by our surroundings.” (IDI S4)</p> <p>“For me, this policy focuses more on students being able to learn effectively because in our classroom, there are those who can learn with designs to see, while others can learn even if their environment is plain.” (FGD S3)</p>

The students stated that they have valued the less distraction in relation to the barewall classroom policy. It was revealed during the conduct of focus group discussions and in-depth interviews that the students said that it became less distracting if there were no decorations posted inside the classroom. Most of them shared their experiences such as being in a classroom that makes them less distracted during the discussion. One of the participants in the person of Forehead (pseudonym) stated that:

“So, nahimo sya na less distraction sya para sa amoa nga naa sa higher grades but para guro sa mga elementary level na mga students, syempre mahimo syang less engaging para sa ilaha ang musulod sa school kay kadalasan baya sauna na elementary ta no kay eskwela mo kay naay gipangprepare si teacher na mga ani-ani sa wall ug malingaw ka.” (IDI_S1)

(So, it was made to be less distracting for us who are in higher grades, but for elementary level students, it might be less engaging for them to enter school because usually back then when we were in elementary, going to school was fun because the teacher would prepare various things on the wall, and you would have fun.)

Chin (pseudonym), a student shared her thoughts on the potential impact of classroom decorations. She explained that if there were decorations, students might be distracted by their bright colors and interesting shapes. This could make it harder to focus on the teacher and the lesson. Instead, she suggested that a plain, distraction-free environment would be more conducive to learning. She stated that:

“Makaingon ko nga nindot ang polisiya sa walay dekorasyon nga classroom kay cozy tan-awon ang classroom. Pinaagi sa pagpatuman niini nga polisiya, makapamenos kini sa mga distraksyon sa mga estudyante kay daghan ang motan-aw sa dekorasyon ug dili magtagad sa ilang klase.” (FGD_S5)

(I can say that this barewall classroom policy is nice since the classroom looks cozy. By implementing this policy, it lessens the distraction of the students since many would look at the design and do not give attention to their classes.)

High school students have revealed their opinions on how the classroom looks in relation to barewall classroom policy. It was noted and observed through their responses during the interviews value of less distraction in their classrooms.

Eyebrows (pseudonym), who believed that there classroom now was a less distraction however she also highlighted how plain the classrooms are. She stated that:

“Ang classroom tan-awon nga plain ug boring kay dili man siya makaiikag tan-awon pag sulod nimo sa classroom kay oo, bland ra gyud siya tan-awon, pero, mas gamay na ang distraksyon karon.” (FGD_S2)

(The classroom looks plain and boring because it is not interesting to look at when you enter the classroom because yes, it is just bland to look at, but well, it was less distraction now.)

Ears (pseudonym), like Forehead and Eyebrows, clearly shared her thoughts about the barewall classroom policy. She said that without decorations, it sometimes feels empty and less engaging. Ears believes that visuals help students stay interested and focused. She worries that some classmates might struggle more without these things. Overall, she feels that the lack of visual support makes learning harder for many students. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo nindot man ug walay decoration ang classroom, hapsay noon tan awun nya hinlo pero naa gihapoy times na ma miss nako ang designs especially if pabuhaton mi ug essay sa among teacher kay usahay didto mi makakuha ug mga ideas sa mga quotes.” (FGD_S3)

(For me, there is no problem with the implementation of the bare wall classroom policy. I feel more refreshed in my surroundings when there are no distractions in my line of sight. However, I believe the impact is greater on students who can learn through the designs in their surroundings.)

Stressing the Importance of Visual Stimulation

This can be according to a belief that visual stimulus is central to learning most especially in a classroom setup. A bare wall classroom policy where students are restricted on the amount of décor they post and the number of teaching aids used inhibits the student’s creativity. Idea and creativity such as the use of colorful displays and instructional posters are useful tools in effective learning. When the content students received is inclusive of such stimulating visuals, then students tend to pay a lot of attention. Thus, using visualization aids in the classroom should be considered very important in the management of the class.

In addition to noting that their classrooms became less distracting, participants highlighted the critical role of visual stimulation in their learning experiences. During interviews, students expressed those visuals, such as charts and decorations, significantly enhance their understanding and engagement with the material. They believe that these elements help to maintain focus and make lessons more relatable. This feedback suggests that while the barewall policy may reduce distractions, it may also overlook the benefits of visual aids that support effective learning. Forehead (pseudonym) a student who learns best through visual stimulation, shared her challenges with the barewall classroom policy. She explained that she often finds it difficult to focus without visual cues like posters or diagrams. While she appreciates the benefits of a distraction-free environment, she suggested that incorporating subtle visual elements, such as simple charts or diagrams, could enhance her learning experience. She stated that:

“So, pag in ani sa among classroom ang challenge sa akoo is dili kay sya ingon nga attractive para sa akoo ang classroom nga naa mi karun. So, too plain lang kay sya para sa amoa. Okay lang para sa amoa pero dili na kaayu in ana ka nindot ang classroom.” (IDI_S1)

(The challenge for me in our classroom is that it is not as attractive to me as the classroom we have now. It is just too plain for us. It is okay for us, but not very aesthetically pleasing. For me, the classroom is not as visually appealing as I would like it to be.)

Nails, a student who shared his perspective on the barewall classroom policy, explained that while he initially found the minimalist environment challenging, he eventually adapted. He discovered that by focusing on the teacher’s words and engaging actively in discussions, he was able to overcome the lack of visual stimulation. Nail’s experience highlights the importance of personal adjustment and active participation in learning, even in a visually minimalist classroom. He stated that:

“Para nako, ang mga hagit nga akong naatubang kay wala ko makakuha ug mga ideya kung maghatag ang among maestra ug task o

essay task kay wala man koy makita nga mga quotes o mga disenyo nga akong mabasihan sa akong essay. Mao nga para nako, kana ang hagit.” (IDI_S5)

(For me, the challenges I have faced is that I was not able to get any ideas when our teacher will give us a task or an essay task because I do not see any quotes or designs which I can base may essay on. So, for me that was the challenge.)

Nose, a student who expressed his feelings about the removal of classroom decorations, shared that he felt lonely without the familiar and comforting visual elements. He explained that the decorations helped him feel connected to his classmates and the classroom environment. While he acknowledged the benefits of a distraction-free space, he suggested that incorporating subtle, personalized elements could help students feel more at ease. He stated that:

“Para sa akin ay di na ako nabibigyan ng motibo sapagkat di ko na mababasa sa mga dingding ang mga sulat kagaya ng, “Honesty is the best policy.” (FGD_S1)

(For me, I am no longer motivated because I can no longer read the writings on the walls like, “Honesty is the best policy.)

Eyebrows, a student who shared her challenges with the barewall classroom policy, explained that the minimalist environment made her feel unmotivated. She found that the lack of visual stimulation made it difficult to stay engaged and interested in the lesson. Eyebrows experience highlights the importance of creating a visually stimulating classroom environment to support student motivation and engagement.

“Ang mga hagit nga akong naatubang kay tan-awon nga plain ra kaayo sa akong panan-aw, mao nga murag wala gyud mosulod sa akong huna-huna kung magdiscuss ang maestra.” (FGD_S2)

(The challenges I have encountered are that it seems too plain in my perspective, so it feels like nothing really enters my mind when the teacher discusses.)

Cheeks, a student who shared her perspective on the impact of visual stimulation in the classroom, explained that the use of diagrams, charts, and other visuals helped her understand the concepts discussed in class more deeply. She found that these visual aids provided a concrete representation of abstract ideas, making it easier to grasp and retain information. Cheeks’ experience emphasizes the importance of incorporating visual elements into classroom instruction to enhance student comprehension. She stated that:

“For me ang challenges na akoang na encounter kay murag sa akoang panan aw kay plain lang gyud kaayu so murag walay mo sulod sa akoang hunahuna te inig mag discuss ang teacher.” (FGD_S4)

(For me, it is easy to learn if I have something to see in my surroundings because it motivates me, but I was surprised, and it took me a while to adjust since I was used to having designs in our classroom before.)

Adhering to Classroom Changes

Structural alteration in classroom can consequently change students’ learning behavior and practices significantly. In the same way, when a teacher changes these options or the format of the whole classroom, it becomes interesting. For instance, the use of technology simplifies the lessons, and the learner can grasp the lesson’s content in a better way. Furthermore, flexibility in arrangement of seats can call for peer collaboration. In aggregate, changes are made to enhance the overall learning process for the benefit of involved learners.

High school students have shared their perspectives on the transition from traditional classrooms to barewall classrooms. They recognized the importance of adapting to this new environment to feel comfortable and focused. Many students noted that the absence of decorations initially felt unsettling, but it encouraged them to find new ways to engage with their learning. They emphasized the need to develop strategies for concentration and to create a sense of belonging despite the stripped-down setting. Overall, their experiences highlight the importance of flexibility and resilience in adapting to significant changes in their learning environment.

Shoulders, a student who shared her observations on the transformation of the classroom, explained that the removal of decorations had a significant impact on the overall atmosphere. She noticed a noticeable shift in focus and concentration among her classmates. While some students initially struggled with the change, Shoulders believed that the barewall classroom ultimately created a more conducive learning environment. Shoulders (pseudonym) have revealed the major transformation of the classroom. She stated that:

“Nabag uhan ko sa tanan because before when I enter the classroom malingaw jud kag tan aw sa mga colorful decorations, karun simple na lang siya.” (IDI_S3)

(I was surprised by everyone because before, when I entered the classroom, I used to enjoy looking at the colorful decorations, but now it is just simple.)

Forehead, a student who shared her thoughts on the impact of classroom decorations, explained that she used to find interesting facts and trivia from the posters and displays on the walls. With the barewall policy, she no longer has this opportunity. While she understands the benefits of a distraction-free environment, she suggests that incorporating subtle educational elements, such as relevant quotes or historical timelines, could provide a learning opportunity while maintaining a minimalist aesthetic. Forehead (pseudonym) also

expressed how she could get trivia or facts on the classroom decorations and now, it became plain, and the walls are bare. She stated that:

“Isip estudyante sa senior high, makita nako nga ang pagkakaroon og barewall classroom dili kaayo makaapekto kanako. Dili ko kaayo interesado sa mga disenyo sa silid-aralan kay ang akong pokus kay sa pagtuon. Samtang ang mga dekorasyon sama sa mga quote ug mga larawan nakatabang sa pagkat-on sa elementarya, ang ilang kakulangan karon nagpasabot nga mawala ang pipila ka trivia ug mga facts nga mahimo unta natong makat-unan gikan niini.” (IDI_S1)

(As a senior high student, I find that having a barewall classroom does not affect me much. I’m not particularly interested in classroom designs because my focus is on studying. While decorations like quotes and pictures helped with learning in elementary, their absence now means losing some trivia and facts that we could learn from them.)

Nails (pseudonym), a student who shared his surprise at the barewall classroom policy, explained that he was initially skeptical about the effectiveness of such a minimalist approach. However, after experiencing the policy firsthand, he noticed a positive change in classroom dynamics. He observed that students were more focused and engaged in their studies, and the overall noise level was significantly reduced. Nails’ experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in improving the learning environment. He stated that:

“Sa una, nabag-ohan ko ngano nga ang DEPED magpatuman ani nga klase nga polisiya kay para nako, dako gyud ni ug tabang ug dugay ko naka-move on kay mas makat-on ko pinaagi sa mga visual representations. Karon nga plain na ang classroom, gi-accept na lang nako ang polisiya kay wala man koy mahimo.” (IDI_S5)

(At first, I was shocked on why DEPED would implement this kind of policy because for me, it really helps and I had long time moving on because I do really learn through visual representations so, now that the classroom is plain, I just let myself adapt the policy because I have nothing to do with it.)

Ears (pseudonym), a student who shared her experiences with classroom design, explained that she was accustomed to having a visually stimulating learning environment. She believed that the decorations and displays in her previous classroom helped her connect with the subject matter and create a more engaging learning experience. While she understood the benefits of a minimalist approach, Ears suggested that incorporating subtle, aesthetically pleasing elements could enhance the overall learning atmosphere. She stated that:

“Actually, naanad jud ko sa among classroom na naay designs kay since elementary ko naa naman jud na unya natingala nalang ko pag ingon sa among maestro na in ani na among classroom, mao to nabag uhan sad ko.” (FGD_S3)

(Actually, I was really used to having designs in our classroom because since elementary school, there were always designs, so I was surprised when our teacher said that our classroom would be like this now, that is why I also had to adjust.)

Enhancing Student Focus

Exercising student focus is a critical element when it comes to teaching to improve the learning field. To ensure students pay much attention, schools can ensure that there is a lot of order as well as little noise. Source: This is about student engagement Goals – Objectives: | Goals/Objectives | Connection in relation to student engagement | Short tasks | Effective in managing students’ interest and focus. Children should take breaks during the studying time because such a step can effectively help them maintain proper focus. Last of all, good sleep and nutrition improve the students’ behavior hence enhances concentration during the learning activities in classroom.

Beyond the physical changes in their classrooms, high school students have noted that the barewall classroom policy has greatly enhanced their concentration and participation in class discussions. By reducing visual distractions, the policy fosters a more conducive learning environment where students can fully focus on the teacher’s instructions and engage more actively in discussions. This improved focus allows them to absorb information more effectively and participate in meaningful dialogue, ultimately deepening their understanding of the subject matter. Students appreciate that this streamlined environment encourages thoughtful interaction and promotes a more immersive learning experience.

Forehead, a student who shared her positive experiences with the barewall classroom policy, explained that the minimalist environment helped her focus better during class. With fewer distractions, she was able to pay closer attention to the teacher and participate more actively in discussions. Forehead’s experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall policy in improving student engagement and learning outcomes. She stated that:

“So, more on the positive side siya ang iyang impact para sa akua it’s because kanang, tinuod jud diay ang ginaingon nga less distraction siya then dili kaayu daghan ug designs inig lingi-lingi nimo ug dili gani gubot sa imong panan aw. So makatarung ka ug eskwela. Tas ang ginaingon nila na once na nakit an nila inyong classroom nga barewall na siya, nindot na sya tan awun, since naa bayay ginaingon nil pag limpyo imong environment, makatuon ka ug tarung.” (IDI_S1)

(The impact is more on the positive side for me because, yes, it is true that it is less distracting and not too cluttered when you look around. It is not messy to look at. So, you can focus on studying. They say that once they see your classroom with bare walls, it looks

nice to see, since they also say that when your environment is clean, you can study well.)

Shoulders (pseudonym), a student who shared her appreciation for the barewall classroom policy, explained that she found the minimalist environment to be refreshing and conducive to learning. She enjoyed the clean and uncluttered space, which helped her feel calm and focused. Shoulders’ experience highlights the positive impact of a minimalist classroom environment on student well-being and academic performance. She stated that:

“As a student, the impact of the barewall policy is maka focus mi slight since plain and simple lang ang design sa palibot.” (IDI_S3)

(As a student, the impact of the barewall policy is that we can focus a bit more easily since the surroundings have a plain and simple design.)

Hands (pseudonym), a student who shared his experiences with the barewall classroom policy, explained that the minimalist environment helped him reduce distractions and focus better. With fewer visual stimuli, he was able to pay closer attention to the teacher’s explanations and participate more actively in class discussions. Hands’ experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in improving student concentration and engagement. He stated that:

“Sa sige nako ’g balik-balik ug sulti, isip usa ka estudyante, dako gyud ni ug positibong epekto nako kay mas naka-focus mi sa diskusyon sa maestra ug dili na kaayo madistract sa among palibot.” (IDI_S4)

(Just like I mentioned repeatedly, as a student, it really brings a positive impact on me because we are more focused on the teacher’s discussion and less distracted by our surroundings.)

Ears (pseudonym), a student who shared her insights on the barewall classroom policy, explained that the minimalist environment created a more conducive learning atmosphere. With fewer distractions, students were able to focus better on the teacher’s words and engage more actively in discussions. Ears’ experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in enhancing student learning outcomes. She stated that:

“So, pareha sa akong giingon, nga as a student, it brings a positive impact on me kay mas focused jud mi sa discussion sa teachers tapos dili na kaayu ma distract sa palibot.” (FGD_S3)

(For me, this policy focuses more on students being able to learn effectively because in our classroom, there are those who can learn with designs to see, while others can learn even if their environment is plain.)

Table 3. Experiences of Teachers with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Following the Removal of Decorations	<p>“The removing of posters, charts, artworks, and other decorations from the wall is the challenge that I particularly encountered since it requires time and effort so as not to cause too much damage to the walls.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“The challenges for me are the removal of materials that we posted on the walls which we putted so much effort in it and it will only be removed because of the policy. Another challenge also is the application of paints so it will look new again because if we will not repaint the walls, it is not pleasing to the eyes of the students since there are marks left by the decorations.” (FGD_T3)</p> <p>“One of the main challenges that I have encountered is lack of resources and funding to support the policy. Without proper materials and tools, it is difficult to create a stimulating learning environment that promotes creativity and collaboration. Another challenge is in terms of rearranging classroom and adopting lesson plans to fit to the new policy.” (IDI_T5)</p> <p>“There are a lot of things to do such as removing the decorations and after that, I have to apply paints to the wall to make it clean and pleasing to see.” (FGD_S5)</p>
Enhancing Student Focus	<p>“The implementation of the barewall classroom policy is a commendable initiative that aims to create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. By removing distractions such as posters, charts and other visual clutter from classroom walls, the policy seeks to create a more focused and conducive space for learning.” (IDI_T5)</p> <p>“The implementation of the barewall classroom policy can have both positive and negative implications, and it is important for educators to consider the unique needs and preferences of their students when implementing such policies.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“Barewall classroom policy is a strategy which aims to create a more focused and conducive learning environment for students.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“This policy is a big help in maintaining the classroom clean and students can focus more on the discussions.” (FGD_T5)</p>
Viewing the Importance of Planning and Preparation	<p>“I prepared my emotional and mental well-being because I felt disappointed with the efforts, I put into preparing the decorations.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“I first identify which items or displays are to be removed and gathered of course, the necessary supplies for removal such as hammers, knives and scrapers.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“To prepare for this change, I carefully took down each decoration. I organized them into labeled bins so they could easily be put back at a later time.” (IDI_T5)</p>

Doing Careful Consideration	<p>“So, the things that I prepared were enough materials for me clean all the things on the wall and I also asked for volunteers during the Brigada Eskwela because I needed people who can help me in cleaning my room as well as repainting the wall.” (FGD_T3)</p> <p>“The preparation I did in removing the decorations is that I evaluate the materials that were posted on the walls on which of them I will keep and which of them I should throw.” (FGD_T5)</p> <p>“The things that I consider in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy is first, is to plan ahead because it develops a timeline in removing decorations and second is to clean and prepare walls in order to consider any repairs or touch-ups needed to ensure the walls are in good condition.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“I must consider the importance of establishing clear guidelines and expectations for student regarding appropriate behavior and conduct in the classroom. Another thing is communication with students and parents is essential in ensuring understanding and compliance with the policy.” (IDI_T5)</p> <p>“In my experience, there are several factors that I considered in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy such as clear communication, alternative resources and stakeholders’ involvement.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“The things that I considered is the learning comfort or the students’ needs because they have different learning styles, and I must create an environment where everyone can learn. Another thing is, I also considered the communication between students, stakeholders and the administration since this policy requires solidarity.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“So, for me, the things that I considered are the arrangement of the tables, the chairs and the usage of secondary paints for wall decoration.” (FGD_T1)</p> <p>“For me, I just considered the color of the classroom and the arrangements of the tables and chairs so it can still be a conducive learning environment.” (FGD_T2)</p>
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Following the Removal of Decorations

It is worthy to note that the literary theme of “Removal of Decorations;” may be associated with the barewall classroom policy by calling for attention learning not distractions. Once decorations are removed the classroom becomes less complex and students can focus solely on the educational process. The purpose of this policy is to establish a situation where everyone understands that the focus should be on education proper, and not on the plethora of logos that can be seen in many schools. Teachers expect that by reducing distraction, the learning achievements of students will be boosted amongst other things. Finally, barewall strategy is aimed at creating a more effective learning environment.

Teachers’ experiences with the implementation of the barewall classroom policy stem from various factors, including the challenges they faced, their preparation efforts, and the thoughtful considerations they made to align their classrooms with the policy. Many teachers encountered obstacles such as resistance from students who preferred visual aids and the need to adjust their teaching methods accordingly. They emphasized the importance of careful planning and preparation in redesigning their classroom spaces to meet the new guidelines while still engaging students effectively. Additionally, teachers considered how to create an inviting atmosphere that fosters learning despite the absence of decorations, showcasing their commitment to adapting their teaching strategies for better educational outcomes. Finger (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her experiences with the barewall classroom policy, explained that removing the posters from her classroom was time-consuming. She found that the process of taking down, storing, and potentially reinstalling the decorations was more labor-intensive than she had anticipated. Finger’s experience highlights the potential logistical challenges involved in implementing a barewall classroom policy. She stated that:

“Ang pagtanggap sa mga poster, tsart, artworks, ug uban pang dekorasyon gikan sa dingding mao ang hagit nga akong nasinati kay kini nagkinahanglan ug oras ug paningkamot aron dili kaayo madaot ang mga dingding.” (IDI_T3)

(The removing of posters, charts, artworks, and other decorations from the wall is the challenge that I particularly encountered since it requires time and effort so as not to cause too much damage to the walls.)

Leg (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her experiences with the barewall classroom policy, explained that the process of removing decorations and repainting the walls was more time-consuming and resource-intensive than she had anticipated. She felt that her efforts to create a visually stimulating learning environment were wasted, as the policy required a completely bare aesthetic. Leg’s experience highlights the potential challenges involved in implementing a barewall classroom policy, particularly in terms of resource allocation and teacher workload. She stated that:

“Ang mga hagit para nako mao ang pagtanggap sa mga materyales nga among gipost sa mga dingding diin among gibutangan ug daghang paningkamot ug kini tangtangan lang tungod sa polisiya. Usa pa ka hagit mao ang pag-apply ug pintura aron magbag-o ug tan-aw ang mga dingding kay kung dili namo pintalan pag-usab, dili kini nindot tan-awon sa mga estudyante kay adunay mga marka nga nahabilin sa mga dekorasyon.” (FGD_T3)

(The challenges for me are the removal of materials that we posted on the walls which we putted so much effort in it and it will only be removed because of the policy. Another challenge also is the application of paints so it will look new again because if we will not repaint the walls, it is not pleasing to the eyes of the students since there are marks left by the decorations.)

Nails (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her challenges with the barewall classroom policy, explained that the policy required additional resources and adjustments to the classroom layout. She found it difficult to create a visually stimulating learning environment

without decorations, and the process of rearranging furniture to accommodate the new aesthetic was time-consuming. Nails' experience highlights the logistical challenges involved in implementing a barewall classroom policy, particularly in terms of resource allocation and classroom design. She stated that:

“Ang usa sa mga pangunang hagit nga akong nasinati mao ang kakulang sa mga kapanguhaan ug pondo aron masuportahan ang polisiya. Kung walay angay nga mga materyales ug mga gamit, lisod ang paghimo og usa ka makapadasig nga palibot sa pagkat-on nga nagpalambo sa pagkamamugnaon ug kolaborasyon. Ang usa pa ka hagit mao ang pag-usab sa paghan-ay sa klasrum ug pag-angay sa mga leksyon aron mohaom sa bag-ong polisiya.” (IDI_T5)

(One of the main challenges that I have encountered is lack of resources and funding to support the policy. Without proper materials and tools, it is difficult to create a stimulating learning environment that promotes creativity and collaboration. Another challenge is in terms of rearranging classroom and adopting lesson plans to fit to the new policy.)

Hair (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her experiences with the barewall classroom policy, emphasized the significant effort required to implement the policy. She explained that the process involved removing existing decorations, repainting the walls, and rearranging furniture to create a minimalist aesthetic. Hair's experience highlights the logistical challenges involved in implementing a barewall classroom policy, particularly in terms of time and resource investment. She stated that:

“Daghan kaayong mga butang nga buhatonon sama sa pagtangtang sa mga dekorasyon ug pagkahuman, kinahanglan nako nga pintalan ang mga dingding aron kini limpyo ug nindot tan-awon.” (FGD_T5)

(There are a lot of things to do such as removing the decorations and after that, I have to apply paints to the wall to make it clean and pleasing to see.)

Enhancing Student Focus

Bare wall classroom policy deals with the policy of having a learning context free from every form of encumbrance and embellishment. As a result of elimination of distractions, students are able to focus more on their lessons and activities a long the day. This approach they are forced to discover more details due to the fact that there are few illustrations as compared to the usual technique of using PowerPoint slides. There is also a realization that complication results in a lot of pressure on the student; therefore, a clean minimalistic environment can help reduce pressure and likely increase performance. In conclusion, this policy is more effective that helps to have a pleasant learning process.

Teachers believe that the barewall classroom policy significantly enhances students' focus during discussions by minimizing visual distractions. With fewer decorations and objects competing for their attention, students can concentrate more effectively on the teacher's words and the content being discussed. This stripped-down environment fosters a more conducive learning atmosphere, allowing students to engage actively and participate in conversations without unnecessary distractions. The simplicity of white walls encourages them to direct their attention to the lesson, promoting deeper understanding and interaction during class. Overall, teachers feel that this approach cultivates a focused and dynamic learning experience for their students.

Nails (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her opinion on the barewall classroom policy, explained that the minimalist environment can promote an inclusive and engaging learning experience. By minimizing visual distractions, the policy can create a more equitable space where all students feel comfortable and focused. Nails' experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in fostering a positive and inclusive learning environment. She stated that:

“Ang pagpatuman sa polisiya sa ‘barewall classroom’ usa ka maayong inisyatibo nga nagtinguha sa paghimo og mas inklusibo ug makapadasig nga palibot sa pagkat-on. Pinaagi sa pagtangtang sa mga distraksyon sama sa mga poster, tsart, ug uban pang visual nga kalat gikan sa mga dingding sa classroom, ang polisiya nagtinguha sa paghimo og mas pokus ug angay nga lugar alang sa pagkat-on.” (IDI_T5)

(The implementation of the barewall classroom policy is a commendable initiative that aims to create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. By removing distractions such as posters, charts and other visual clutter from classroom walls, the policy seeks to create a more focused and conducive space for learning.)

Elbow (pseudonym), a teacher who shared his thoughts on the barewall classroom policy, emphasized the importance of considering students' individual learning preferences. He explained that while the minimalist environment can be beneficial for some students, it may pose challenges for others who require visual stimulation. Elbow's experience highlights the need for a balanced approach that accommodates the diverse learning needs of all students. He stated that:

“Ang pagpatuman sa polisiya sa ‘barewall classroom’ mahimong adunay positibo ug negatibong mga implikasyon, ug importante alang sa mga magtutudlo nga tagdon ang talagsaong mga panginahanglan ug mga gusto sa ilang mga estudyante sa dihang ipatuman ang ingon nga mga polisiya.” (IDI_T2)

(The implementation of the barewall classroom policy can have both positive and negative implications, and it is important for educators to consider the unique needs and preferences of their students when implementing such policies.)

Belly (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her experiences with the barewall classroom policy, emphasized the positive impact on the teaching and learning process. She explained that the minimalist environment created a more focused and engaging atmosphere, allowing for more effective instruction and student participation. Belly's experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience. She stated that:

"Ang polisiya sa 'barewall classroom' usa ka estratehiya nga nagtinguha sa paghimo og mas pokus ug angay nga palibot sa pagkat-on alang sa mga estudyante." (FGD_T4)

(Barewall classroom policy is a strategy which aims to create a more focused and conducive learning environment for students.)

Hair (pseudonym), a teacher who shared her perspective on the barewall classroom policy, emphasized its significance in creating a more focused and conducive learning environment for students. She explained that by minimizing visual distractions, the policy allowed students to concentrate better on the teacher's words and the content of the discussion. Hair's experience highlights the potential benefits of a barewall classroom policy in enhancing student learning and engagement. She stated that:

"Kini nga polisiya dako kaayo ug tabang sa pagmintinar sa kalimpyo sa classroom ug ang mga estudyante makapokus na sa mga diskusyon." (FGD_T5)

(This policy is a big help in maintaining the classroom clean and students can focus more on the discussions.)

Viewing the Importance of Planning and Preparation

Secondary school teachers stated that their experiences in removing the decorations inside the classroom, requires planning and preparation. It was revealed during the conduct of focus group discussions and in-depth interviews that the teachers prepare themselves from removing the decorations up to repainting the classroom again. One of the participants in the person of Elbow (pseudonym) stated that:

"Giandam nako ang akong emosyonal ug mental nga kahintang kay nabati nako ang kapakyasan sa akong mga paningkamot sa pag-andam sa mga dekorasyon." (IDI_T2)

(I prepared my emotional and mental well-being because I felt disappointed with the efforts, I put into preparing the decorations.)

Finger (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of choosing which decorations to remove and which to keep. She explained that certain decorations can enhance a space's ambiance and overall appeal, while others may create clutter or detract from the desired aesthetic. By carefully considering the impact of each decoration, individuals can curate a more harmonious and inviting environment. She stated that:

"Una, akong ilhon kung unsang mga butang o display ang tangtangon ug tigumon, siyempre, ang mga kinahanglanon nga gamit alang sa pagtanggap sama sa martilyo, kutsilyo, ug scraper." (IDI_T3)

(I first identify which items or displays are to be removed and gathered of course, the necessary supplies for removal such as hammers, knives and scrapers.)

Nails (pseudonym) also discussed the value of organizing removed decorations. She emphasized that by properly arranging these items, teachers can easily locate and access them when needed. This organization not only streamlines the process of finding specific decorations but also helps in maintaining a sense of order and efficiency within the classroom environment. She stated that:

"Aron mag-andam alang niini nga kausaban, akong hinayhinay nga gitangtang ang matag dekorasyon. Ako kini gipang-organisar sa mga bin nga adunay label aron dali ra kini ibalik unya." (IDI_T5)

(To prepare for this change, I carefully took down each decoration. I organized them into labeled bins so they could easily be put back later.)

Leg (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of preparing necessary materials before removing classroom decorations. She emphasized the need to have appropriate tools, such as ladders, step stools, and cleaning supplies, readily available. This preparation ensures a smooth and efficient removal process, minimizing any potential damage to the decorations or the classroom itself. She revealed that:

"Ang mga butang nga akong giandam igo na nga mga materyales para limpyo tanan nga mga butang sa dingding ug nangayo usab ko og mga boluntaryo sa panahon sa Brigada Eskwela kay nanginahanglan ko og mga tawo nga makatabang nako sa paglimpyo sa akong kwarto ug pag-repaint sa dingding." (FGD_T3)

(So, the things that I prepared were enough materials for me clean all the things on the wall and I also asked for volunteers during the Brigada Eskwela because I needed people who can help me in cleaning my room as well as repainting the wall.)

Hair (pseudonym) agreed that it's important to carefully choose which materials to remove and which to keep in the classroom. She said that some items are helpful for learning, while others can be distracting. Hair believes that keeping a few key visuals can make lessons more engaging. She feels that it's all about finding the right balance. By selecting materials wisely, the classroom can still

support students' focus and understanding. She stated that:

“Ang akong preparasyon sa pagtanggap sa mga dekorasyon mao nga akong gi-evaluate ang mga materyales nga gibutang sa mga dingding kung asa niini akong itago ug asa ang akong ilabay.” (FGD_T5)

(The preparation I did in removing the decorations is that I evaluate the materials that were posted on the walls on which of them I will keep and which of them I should throw.)

Doing Careful Consideration

Every challenge faced by secondary teachers provided valuable insights that prompted them to consider both their own needs and those of their students. These challenges encouraged teachers to engage in careful decision-making regarding the classroom setup. For instance, they had to think critically about how to create an environment that minimizes distractions while still supporting effective learning. By reflecting on their experiences, teachers realized the importance of balancing functionality with a sense of comfort for students. Ultimately, these considerations helped them design classrooms that foster a positive and productive learning atmosphere.

Elbow (pseudonym) shared his challenges with the barewall classroom policy. He mentioned that the absence of decorations made the room feel cold and uninviting. Elbow found it difficult to keep students engaged without visual aids to capture their interest. He also worried that some students struggled to focus on such a stark environment. He stated that:

“Ang mga butang nga akong gi-considera ap ag-implementar sa barewall classroom policy mao ang una, magplano daan kay kini nag-develop og timeline sa pagtanggap sa mga dekorasyon ug ikaduha, limpyo ug andamon ang mga dingding aron ma-considera ang bisan unsang mga repairs o touch-ups nga kinahanglan aron masiguro nga ang mga dingding naa sa maayong kondisyon.” (IDI_T2)

(The things that I consider in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy is first, is to plan ahead because it developed a timeline in removing decorations and second is to clean and prepare walls in order to consider any repairs or touch-ups needed to ensure the walls are in good condition.)

Nails (pseudonym) emphasized the need for clear guidelines to manage student behavior effectively. She explained that having set rules helps students know what is expected of them. Nails also highlighted the importance of communicating with parents about these guidelines. She believes that keeping parents informed can help reinforce good behavior at home. She stated that:

“Kinahanglan nako hunahunaon ang kahinungdanon ap ag-establisar og klaro nga mga giya ug gilauman alang sa mga estudyante bahin sa angay nga pamatasan ug paglihok sa sulod sa klase. Usa pa, ang komunikasyon sa mga estudyante ug ginikanan mahinungdanon aron masiguro ang pagsabot ug pagsunod sa polisiya.” (IDI_T5)

(I must consider the importance of establishing clear guidelines and expectations for student regarding appropriate behavior and conduct in the classroom. Another thing is communication with students and parents is essential in ensuring understanding and compliance with the policy.)

Finger (pseudonym) discussed the importance of communication with stakeholders when implementing the barewall classroom policy. She stated that keeping everyone informed—like teachers, parents, and school staff—helps everyone understand the changes. Finger believes that open discussions can address concerns and gather feedback. This way, everyone can work together to support students in the new environment. She stated that:

“Sa akong kasinatian, adunay daghang mga butang nga akong gikonsiderar sa pagpatuman sa polisiya sa barewall classroom sama sa klaro nga komunikasyon, alternatibong mga kapanguhaan, ug pag-apil sa mga stakeholders.” (IDI_T3)

(In my experience, there are several factors that I considered in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy such as clear communication, alternative resources and stakeholders' involvement.)

Belly (pseudonym) shared her thoughts on the importance of students' learning comfort during the barewall classroom policy's implementation. She emphasized that creating a comfortable environment is essential for effective learning. Belly also highlighted the need to communicate with stakeholders, including parents and teachers, about these changes. She believes that involving everyone helps address concerns and improves support for students. She stated that:

“Ang mga butang nga akong gikonsiderar mao ang kahupayan sa pagkat-on o ang mga panginahanglan sa mga estudyante tungod kay sila adunay lain-lain estilo sa pagkat-on, ug kinahanglan nako maghimo og usa ka palibot diin ang tanan makakat-on. Usa pa, gikonsiderar usab nako ang komunikasyon tali sa mga estudyante, mga stakeholders, ug ang administrasyon tungod kay kini nga polisiya nagkinahanglan og panaghiusa.” (FGD_T4)

(The things that I considered is the learning comfort or the students' needs because they have different learning styles, and I must create an environment where everyone can learn. Another thing is, I also considered the communication between students, stakeholders and the administration since this policy requires solidarity.)

Mouth (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of how tables and chairs are arranged in the classroom. He said that a good setup can

help students feel more comfortable and focused. Mouth also mentioned that the colors used in the room matter, as they can affect mood and attention. He believes that thoughtful arrangement and color choices create a better learning space. He stated that:

“Para nako, ang mga butang nga akong giisip mao ang paghan-ay sa mga lamesa, ang mga lingkuranan, ug ang paggamit sa mga sekundaryong pinal para sa dekorasyon sa dingding.” (FGD_T1)

Head (pseudonym) discussed how important it is to arrange tables and chairs properly to create a good learning environment. He stated that a well-organized classroom helps students focus better and work together. Head believes that the right setup can make discussions easier and encourage participation. He emphasized that comfort and space are key for effective learning. He stated that:

“Para nako, giisip ra nako ang kolor sa classroom ug ang paghan-ay sa mga lamesa ug mga lingkuranan aron magpabilin nga usa ka maayong palibot para sa pagkat-on.” (FGD_T2)

(For me, I just considered the color of the classroom and the arrangements of the tables and chairs so it can still be a conducive learning environment.)

Research Question No. 2: How do the teachers and students cope up with the challenges they faced with regards to the implementation of the barewall classroom policy?

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 is presented in Table 4 and Table 5. Participants had their responses on how they cope with the challenges they faced in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy. From the answers of the participants, eight major themes emerged: embracing acceptance, being adaptable to changes, adjusting flexibly to changes, understanding the situation, participating community involvement, ensuring technology integration, establishing clear communication and creating a conducive learning space.

Table 4. Coping Mechanisms of Students with the Challenges of the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Embracing Acceptance	<p>“So, we have gotten used to entering our classroom or being in the classroom without any design. So, it has become a norm in our classroom even though there are others who are not into that plain look because that’s what they see, but we cannot do anything about it.” (IDI_S1)</p> <p>“I overcome the changes that occur in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy by accepting that there will be changes that will happen.” (IDI_S3)</p> <p>“So, at first, we felt strange because it seemed like we were being singled out by our environment, like we were different. But as time went by, we also realized that this is for improvement, for the benefit of all, for higher quality education, enabling the DepEd and students to become more effective.” (IDI_S4)</p> <p>“I just suit myself with the new policy since it is also helpful for me as a student.” (FGD_S5)</p>
Adaptable to Changes	<p>“So, for us, we do not really notice whether we have a design or not in our classroom. For me, I do not really notice if our classroom has decorations or not. Yes, we talk about it, but when implementing this order or policy, we discussed it with our classmates, and we realized that this is our classroom. We talked about it, and we had a vote where some were more positive about it, while others were negative.” (IDI_S1)</p> <p>“I never let my emotions drive me or bring me down. I did not dwell on the challenges as if they were bringing me down.” (IDI_S2)</p> <p>“So, by always thinking that the bare wall classroom policy is a way to a more developed education, that is always what I have in mind just to address our challenges.” (IDI_S4)</p> <p>“For me, instead of shouting, I just divert my attention to the class so that I can learn more.” (FGD_S4)</p>
Adjusting Flexibly to Changes	<p>“My strategies are, as I have said, to always be flexible and normalize changes because change is the only constant. So, that is really it. Let us just go with the flow together.” (IDI_S2)</p> <p>“So, one of the strategies that I always do is to always put in my mind that all the things are usually for the bene of everyone. That is what we teach to the children.” (IDI_4)</p> <p>“For me, I am just being adaptable and flexible to changes.” (IDI_S5)</p> <p>“For me, I became open to changes, and I allowed myself to be flexible in different environments so that I would not have a hard time.” (FGD_S4)</p>
Understanding the Situation	<p>“So, we have our opinions about this, but then we can’t do anything because it was ordered by the DepEd, which is higher than us. So, as students, we just must cooperate with their decision because we know that they have insights that go beyond our understanding. Yes, our teacher was really surprised by our classroom. Our classroom used to be different, the color was all white and now it’s different.” (IDI_S1)</p> <p>“I tried to understand the situation and the deeper meaning of that policy, what is its purpose because for example, it just disappeared in the classroom but what is the deeper implementation of their policy. So, I understood it in order to deal with my own sentiments.” (IDI_S2)</p> <p>“I also understand their side since the designs can be distracting as well.” (FGD_S5)</p>

Embracing Acceptance

The best inclusion practice in a barewall classroom policy means that an education setting should embrace handling diversity through students accepting and embracing each other. For instance, a barewall classroom, that is a class that lacks many drawings or paintings, can do much to stop the learners from getting distracted. This policy features free speech so that students feel like they belong to a

community. Basically, this means that by accepting different ideas and backgrounds, teachers may help their students develop respect for other students. In conclusion, this strategy supports development of a positive environment for everyone in the society and within and around institutions.

Acceptance emerged as a fundamental factor for students in implementing the barewall classroom policy. During interviews, participants expressed that embracing this mindset helped them navigate the challenges they faced. Forehead (pseudonym) shared her experience of adjusting to a plain classroom, explaining that over time, she learned to adapt to the new environment. She mentioned that accepting the situation was crucial since she felt there was little, she could do to change it. By focusing on her studies and finding ways to engage with the material, she discovered that acceptance allowed her to maintain a positive attitude despite the lack of visual stimulation. She stated that:

“So, nasanay nalang mi nga pagsulod namo sa classroom is wala na syay, design. So, pasanayay nalang jud siya sa inyuhang classroom though naay uban student nga dili kay sila into plain kay ang ilang makita pero wala natay mahimo.” (IDI_S1)

(So, we have gotten used to entering our classroom or being in the classroom without any design. So, it has become a norm in our classroom even though there are others who are not into that plain look because that is what they see, but we cannot do anything about it)

Shoulders (pseudonym) emphasized her acceptance of the barewall classroom policy and the changes it brought. She stated that embracing change is an important part of learning and growing. Shoulders recognized that while the classroom may look different, the focus should remain on education. She believes that adapting to this new environment can lead to better concentration and engagement. She stated that:

“I overcome the changes that occur in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy by accepting that there will be changes na mahitabo.” (IDI_S3)

(I overcome the changes that occur in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy by accepting that there will be changes that will happen.)

Shoulders (pseudonym) emphasized her acceptance of the barewall classroom policy and the changes it brought. She stated that embracing change is an important part of learning and growing. Shoulders recognized that while the classroom may look different, the focus should remain on education. She believes that adapting to this new environment can lead to better concentration and engagement. He stated that:

“So, at first, we felt strange jud kay nabag uhan man mi sa palibot murag maka ingon mi nga murag lahi jud, haw ang among pananaw but by the time goes by narealize sad namo na kini siya para ni sa kabag uhan, para sa kaayuhan sa tanan, para sa more quality education, maka produce ang DepEd ug mga estudyante na more effective students.” (IDI_S4)

(So, at first, we felt strange because it seemed like we were being singled out by our environment, like we were different. But as time went by, we also realized that this is for improvement, for the benefit of all, for higher quality education, enabling the DepEd and students to become more effective.)

Chin (pseudonym) explained how the barewall classroom policy has helped her with her studies. She stated that without distractions, she can focus more on the teacher and the lessons. Chin found that the plain walls make it easier for her to think clearly and understand the material. She feels that this setup has improved her ability to participate in class discussions. She stated that:

“Giangay ra nako ang akong kaugalingon sa bag-ong polisiya kay makatabang man kini nako isip usa ka estudyante.” (FGD_S5)

(I just suit myself with the new policy since it is also helpful for me as a student.)

Adaptable to Changes

The general theme concerning changes within the course of the barewall classrooms policy is flexibility. This policy helps a teacher to adopt a flexible learning environment since there should be minimal disturbance emanating from what is on the walls. Thus, maintaining the area of the classroom relatively plain, the teachers can freely transform the environment in accordance to the type of learning-teaching process needed. This makes it easier for students to learn and it offers the teachers more ways of passing information. All in all, barewall classroom requires day to day changes that augurs well for a classroom since it facilitates changes where they are necessary.

To become adaptable, one must possess a strong belief and the courage to accept changes. During the interviews, participants shared their experiences of adjusting to the barewall classroom policy. Forehead (pseudonym) revealed that her strong viewpoint about the policy was a key factor in helping her cope with the challenges she encountered. She emphasized that believing in the potential benefits of the policy allowed her to approach the changes with a positive mindset. Forehead stated that this perspective helped her remain open to new ways of learning, ultimately making the transition smoother and more manageable for her. She stated that:

“So, sa amoa is dili kaayu namo mapansin nga naa or wala nay design among classroom. So, para sa akua, dili kay nako mapansin

nga naay kabag uhan ug way kabag uhan ang among classroom. Yes, naga talk mi ana but pag-implement ani na order or policy, so naisturyahan namo siya, syempre sa among mga classmate.” (IDI_S1)

(So, for us, we do not really notice whether we have a design or not in our classroom. For me, I do not really notice if our classroom has decorations or not. Yes, we talk about it, but when implementing this order or policy, we discussed it with our classmates, and we realized that this is our classroom. We talked about it, and we had a vote where some were more positive about it, while others were negative.)

Eyes (pseudonym) shared her coping mechanism for dealing with the challenges of the barewall classroom policy by emphasizing the importance of not letting her emotions control her thoughts. She stated that staying calm and focused helps her tackle difficulties more effectively. Eyes believes that recognizing her feelings allows her to maintain a clear perspective on her studies. By prioritizing her learning over emotional responses, she feels more empowered to adapt to the changes. She stated that:

“Kanang never nako gidamdang or gi let akong emotion nga mag drive sa akong. So, wala ko nagpadala sa kabag uhan ug nagpa-down.” (IDI_S2)

(I never let my emotions drive me or bring me down. I did not dwell on the challenges as if they were bringing me down.)

Hands (pseudonym) talked about how he managed his thoughts regarding the barewall classroom policy. He stated that he took time to reflect on the changes and what they meant for his learning. Hands found it helpful to focus on the positives, like fewer distractions in the classroom. He also mentioned discussing his feelings with friends, which made him feel less alone. He stated that:

“So, one of the solutions of this type of policy, there are challenges therefore implementing a policy is that by always thinking that the barewall classroom policy is a way to the more developed education. Mao ra jud na always akong gihuna huna para lang ma solusyonan.” (IDI_S4)

(So, by always thinking that the bare wall classroom policy is a way to a more developed education, that is always what I have in mind just to address our challenges.)

Cheeks (pseudonym) shared how she coped with the challenges of the barewall classroom policy by focusing her thoughts on the discussions instead of the policy itself. She stated that when she feels distracted, she tries to pay attention to what the teacher is saying. By concentrating on the lesson, she finds it easier to stay engaged and learn. Cheeks believes that this shift in focus helps her overcome any frustration she feels about the plain classroom. She stated that:

“For me, instead na magyawayaw ko, gi divert nalang nako akong huna huna sa klase arun daghan sad ko ug ma learn.” (FGD_S4)

(For me, instead of shouting, I just divert my attention to the class so that I can learn more.)

Adjusting Flexibly to Changes

This paper identifies the role of loose coupling, the ability of the organization to be flexible in its response to changing circumstances, in the context of a barewall classroom policy. This policy ensure there is less interference ensuring that the teachers and students are able to easily change between concepts or methods easily. If the walls are blank, it leaves room for innovation in education and lesson and other activities thus can be adjusted quickly. Teachers may modify these displays or any other items to fit the learning process, something not feasible when limited by the decorations.

Flexibility involves more than just recognizing the positive aspects of a situation. High school students shared that being adaptable to changes has helped them cope with the challenges posed by the barewall classroom policy. Participants emphasized that adjusting flexibly allows them to discover the brighter side of every experience. Eyes (pseudonym) illustrated this by explaining how she learned to fit into the new environment by embracing change. She stated that by keeping an open mind and focusing on her studies, she was able to overcome her initial discomfort and find ways to engage more effectively in the classroom. This adaptability not only improved her learning experience but also encouraged a more positive outlook on the changes around her.

“Ang akong strategies kay being flexible jud or inormalize jud ang changes kay changes is the only constant man daw. So, mao ra jud to siya. Sabay- sabay ra jud ta unya go with the flow.” (IDI_S2)

(My strategies are, as I have said, to always be flexible and normalize changes because change is the only constant. So, that is really it. Let us just go with the flow together.)

Hands (pseudonym) expressed his thoughts on the benefits of the barewall classroom policy. He stated that the lack of distractions helps him focus better on the lessons. Hands believes that this simpler environment encourages him to engage more with the teacher and participate in discussions. He also mentioned that it allows him to think more clearly and absorb information more effectively. Overall, he feels that the policy has had a positive impact on his learning experience. He stated that:

“So, one of the strategies na amoang gi own na akong ginabuhay permente, is that ang ginabutang nako sa akong huna huna na kini tanang mga butang nga is, uhm usani siya sa mga butang para sa kaayuhan sa tanan. Mao gyud na ang ginatudlo sa mga children.” (IDI_S4)

(So, one of the strategies that I always do is to always put in my mind that all the things are usually for the benefit of everyone. That is what we teach to the children.)

Nails (pseudonym) talked about how being flexible helped him cope with the challenges he faced. He stated that adjusting his mindset made it easier to accept the changes in the classroom. Nails found that being open to new ways of learning helped him stay focused. He mentioned that flexibility allowed him to find solutions when things got tough. He stated that:

“Para sa akoo, nagapakita lang ko og pagka-adaptable ug flexible sa mga kausaban.” (IDI_S5)

(For me, I am just being adaptable and flexible to changes.)

Cheeks (pseudonym) shared how she learned to be flexible to fit into the new classroom environment. She stated that being open to change helped her understand the situation better. By adjusting her approach to learning, she found it easier to focus on her studies. Cheeks realized that embracing flexibility allowed her to adapt to the barewall policy. Overall, she feels that this attitude has made her a stronger student. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo kay naging open ko for changes and I let myself being flexible to different environment para sad dili kaayu ko maglisud.” (FGD_S4)

(For me, I became open to changes and I allowed myself to be flexible in different environments so that I would not have a hard time.)

Understanding the Situation

Understanding the situation about bare wall classroom policy underlines the need to foster a positive learning climate. Classroom with no qualities and other items hung on the walls promotes develop disconnection and uninspiring to the students. We therefore need to be aware of the consequences that this environment has on motivation of students. In this way, educators will develop an appreciation for the children's, basic needs, which will inform the environment, they are provided with in order to learn. In conclusion, teaching and learning environment has implication to students' welfare and academic achievement.

To truly understand a situation, one must first gain knowledge about it. Secondary students revealed that understanding the barewall classroom policy helped them cope with the challenges they faced. During interviews, participants explained that knowing the reasons behind the policy made it easier to accept. They felt that this understanding allowed them to adapt better and find ways to succeed in the new environment.

Forehead (pseudonym) emphasized how important it is to understand the situation and work together as students when implementing the barewall classroom policy. She stated that when everyone cooperates, it makes the transition smoother for everyone. Forehead believes that understanding the reasons behind the policy helps students accept it better. She also mentioned that teamwork can create a more positive learning environment. She stated that:

“So, naa mi amoang opinion about sa in ani, but then wala mi mahimo kay gi order naman siya sa DepEd, sa ato pa naay mas taas sa amoa, so isip estudyante, amoa nalang is mo-cooperate nalang sa ilahang policy kay kabalo man mi nga naa silay mga insights na mas malabwan pa beyond lang pud sa amoang mga understanding. Yes, ang among maestro giingnan jud namo siya nga maota sa atong classroom sir oy. Bago na in ana among classroom, nalahi ug color, puti rajud na tanan unya pangita sa atong room sir oy.” (IDI_S1)

(So, we have our opinions about this, but then we cannot do anything because it was ordered by the DepEd, which is higher than us. So, as students, we just must cooperate with their decision because we know that they have insights that go beyond our understanding. Yes, our teacher was really surprised by our classroom. Our classroom used to be different, the color was all white and now it is different.)

Eyes (pseudonym) explained the reason behind the barewall classroom policy and why decorations should be removed. She stated that the policy aims to reduce distractions so students can focus better on their lessons. Eyes mentioned that a plain classroom helps everyone concentrate on the teacher's words and the materials being taught. She believes that fewer decorations can lead to better learning outcomes. She stated that:

“I tried to understand the situation unsa jud ang deeper meaning ato nga polisiya. Unsa juy purpose ana kay pananglitan nanga wala lang sa classroom pero unsa jud diay ang deeper nga ilahang ano ilahang implement nga policy. So, gi understand nako to deal with my own sentiments.” (IDI_S2)

(I tried to understand the situation and the deeper meaning of that policy, what is its purpose because for example, it just disappeared in the classroom but what is the deeper implementation of their policy. So, I understood it to deal with my own sentiments.)

Chin (pseudonym) shared her understanding of the barewall classroom policy and how decorations can be distracting. She stated that when there are too many designs in the classroom, it's hard for her to focus on the lessons. Chin believes that a simpler environment helps her pay attention to what the teacher is saying. She feels that reducing distractions allows her to learn better. She stated that:

“Ginasabot sad nako ilang side since distraction sad bitaw ang mga design.” (FGD_S5)

(I also understand their side since the designs can be distracting as well.)

Table 5. Coping Mechanisms of Teachers with the Challenges of the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Participating Community Involvement	<p>“In seeking assistance in designing my classroom, I consulted with the school principal to ask for guidance and support and other than that, I also engage with students and parents as I need manpower in repainting the classroom wall.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“I requested the parents of my students and my students themselves by sending message in our FB messenger or group chat.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“So still, I sought the assistance of my co teachers and also by reading the memorandum from the department of education.” (IDI_T4)</p> <p>“I started by reaching out to my colleagues who had experience in designing classroom and implementing educational policies. (IDI_T5)</p> <p>So, I sought assistance by approaching the volunteers during the Brigada Eskwela.” (FGD_T3)</p> <p>“For me to finish designing my classroom in a short span of time, I seek assistance with my students since I will have a hard time finishing it if I am the only one to do it. Also, I seek guidance with the principal on what are the do’s and don’ts in designing my classroom in line with the barewall classroom policy.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“I seek assistance to the students and their parents in designing my classroom especially in repainting the walls.” (FGD_T5)</p>
Ensuring Technology Integration	<p>“I always have in mind that classroom should be conducive for learning. Second is, incorporating technology in teaching to enhance student engagement and make learning more interactive. Lastly, implementing hands-on activities for fostering active learning and critical thinking skills.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“One effective approach is to incorporate hands- on activities and interactive learning experience. Another method is to utilize technology as a tool for engagement.” (IDI_T5)</p> <p>“Alternative methods using technology through cellphone, TV and laptop as well as reading materials to help aid the learning of the students.” (FGD_T1)</p> <p>“To create a stimulating and engaging learning environment I tend to improve and incorporate pictures and images in my power point presentation of my topic being discussed.” (FGD_T2)</p> <p>“The alternative methods I used in creating a stimulating and engaging learning environment is I incorporated technology in my discussion because I believe that it is a big help in order for the students to learn.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“The methods I incorporated is that I used is that I incorporated interactive technology such as digital displays and educational apps which can help the students to enhance their learning experience.” (FGD_T5)</p>
Establishing Clear Communication	<p>“By telling them that we should follow the policy released by the DepEd and of course and it is beneficial to us teachers since we cannot spend money to purchase decorations.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“I engaged with parents and students in the conversation about barewall classroom policy through meeting. I addressed their questions and concerns emphasizing the advantages of this policy.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“So, I did communicate the changes inside our classrooms. As I have said, it is important to speak with your colleagues in order to implement this policy well.” (IDI_T4)</p> <p>“By organizing the meeting with the students and with their respective parents to explain the policy as well as highlighting its positive impact to the students.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“By simply explaining to them the benefits and its impact for the students and for us, as teachers.” (FGD_T5)</p>
Creating a Conducive Learning Space	<p>“As what I have said earlier, I created a flexible learning space that will cater the different learning preferences of my students.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“Fostering open communication with students and creating a safe space for them to express their thoughts and feelings can help maintain a positive atmosphere in the classroom and by actively listening to student concern.” (IDI_T5)</p> <p>“So, by ensuring the classroom has a well ventilated wall to give students a conducive learning environment through nice paints and with that learners can maintain the cleanliness of the classroom by wiping the wall.” (FGD_T1)</p> <p>“For me, decorations and posters were not the mere method to maintain a positive environment, we can also create a supportive and positive environment by creating a classroom norms, rules and policy.” (FGD_T2)</p> <p>“By having open communication with my students as well as making the classroom a conducive space for all types of students.” (FGD_T4)</p>

Participating Community Involvement

It is crucial for a positive learning environment a person engages in community involvement. The barewall classroom policy suggests that the schools should maintain space- Bare walls to exert positive behaviors among students. This is good for students so that they can focus on their work and notice more about their environment. This way, schools can foster people’s participation in the decoration of the space since the artists who are to be hired may also be residents in the given community. They are also my students feel at home in the classroom as well as developing pride in them.

Settling and designing classrooms in line with the barewall classroom policy involved various tasks, from removing decorations to cleaning and repainting the walls. Teachers recognized that community involvement was crucial to make these changes lighter and more manageable. During the interviews, participants discussed how seeking assistance helped them cope with the challenges of

implementing the policy. Elbow (pseudonym) revealed that the principal's guidance and support had a significant impact on successfully putting the policy into practice. He stated that having strong leadership made it easier for teachers to navigate the changes and encouraged collaboration within the school community, ultimately fostering a smoother transition to the new classroom environment. He stated that:

“Sa pagpangayo og tabang sa pagdesinyo sa akong silid-aralan, nakigkonsulta ko sa prinsipal sa eskwelahan aron mangayo og giya ug suporta. Gawas ni ana, nakig-engage usab ko sa mga estudyante ug ginikanan kay kinahanglan nako ang manpower sa pag-repaint sa dingding sa silid-aralan.” (IDI_T2)

(In seeking assistance in designing my classroom, I consulted with the school principal to ask for guidance and support and other than that, I also engage with students and parents as I need manpower in repainting the classroom wall.)

Finger (pseudonym) explained how she reached out to the parents of her students to help design the classrooms in line with the barewall classroom policy. She stated that involving parents was important because they can offer valuable support and ideas. Finger believes that their input helps create a better learning environment for everyone. By working together, she felt they could overcome the challenges of the new policy. She stated that:

“Nangayo ko og tabang sa mga ginikanan sa akong mga estudyante ug sa akong mga estudyante mismo pinaagi sa pagpadala og mensahe sa among FB Messenger o group chat.” (IDI_T3)

(I requested the parents of my students and my students themselves by sending message in our FB messenger or group chat.)

Just like Elbow, Palm (pseudonym) shared that seeking help from his fellow teachers would aid him in designing his classroom. He highlighted the importance of carefully reading the memorandum to understand the policy fully. Palm believes that knowing the details helps him find the best solutions for the classroom setup. He stated that collaborating with colleagues can bring fresh ideas and support. He stated that:

“Busa, nangayo gihapon ko og tabang sa akong mga kauban nga magtutudlo ug pinaagi sa pagbasa sa memorandum gikan sa Department of Education.” (IDI_T4)

(So still, I sought the assistance of my co teachers and also by reading the memorandum from the department of education.)

Nails (pseudonym) expressed how she reached out to her co-teachers for help, especially those with experience in implementing educational policies. She stated that their insights were valuable in navigating the challenges of the barewall classroom policy. Nails believes that learning from her colleagues can help her make better decisions for her classroom. She found their advice helpful in creating an effective learning environment. She stated that:

“Nagsugod ko sa pagduol sa akong mga kauban nga adunay kasinatian sa pagdesinyo sa silid-aralan ug sa pagpatuman sa mga polisiya sa edukasyon.” (IDI_T5)

(I started by reaching out to my colleagues who had experience in designing classroom and implementing educational policies.)

Leg (pseudonym) recalled how she reached out to Brigada volunteers for help in making her classroom plain and simple to follow the barewall classroom policy. She stated that the volunteers were eager to assist and provided valuable support in removing decorations and cleaning. Leg appreciated their willingness to help create a better learning space for students. She believes that working with the community made the process easier and more effective. She stated that:

“Busa, nangayo ko og tabang pinaagi sa pagduol sa mga boluntaryo sa panahon sa Brigada Eskwela.” (FGD_T3)

(So, I sought assistance by approaching the volunteers during the Brigada Eskwela.)

Belly (pseudonym) emphasized how important it is for students to help remove decorations from the walls. She stated that doing it alone would take a lot of time and be very difficult. Belly believes that having students assist her makes the process faster and more fun. She appreciated their support and teamwork in making the classroom ready for the barewall policy. She stated that:

“Aron matapos nako ang pagdesinyo sa akong silid-aralan sa mubo nga panahon, nangayo ko og tabang sa akong mga estudyante kay lisod kaayo nako kuni matapos kung ako ra ang magbuhat. Gawas ni ana, nangayo usab ko og giya sa prinsipal kung unsay mga angay ug dili angay buhaton sa pagdesinyo sa akong silid-aralan nga uyon sa barewall classroom policy.” (FGD_T4)

(For me to finish designing my classroom in a short span of time, I seek assistance with my students since I will have a hard time finishing it if I am the only one to do it. Also, I seek guidance with the principal on what are do's and don'ts in designing my classroom in line with the barewall classroom policy.)

Hair (pseudonym) agreed that having students help with cleaning and designing the classroom is very important for teachers. She stated that assistance makes the work much easier and quicker. Hair believes that when students get involved, they also take more ownership of their space. She feels that this teamwork creates a positive atmosphere in the classroom. She stated that:

“Nangayo ko og tabang sa mga estudyante ug sa ilang mga ginikanan sa pagdesinyo sa akong silid-aralan, labi na sa pag-repaint sa mga dingding.” (FGD_T5)

(I seek assistance to the students and their parents in designing my classroom especially in repainting the walls.)

Ensuring Technology Integration

The concept behind barewall classroom policy is to ensure that the environment of learning is as simple as possible. It is useful to employ in this way in order to avoid disruptions that might hinder students from using the technology; as the former facilitates concentration on the tools. Since there are less objects to hang on the walls, teachers are able to incorporate the use of screens as well as interaction boards. This setup makes students to use technology in their learning thus improving their experience. In general, the specified barewall classroom has the advantages of providing a better technological integration into the class.

Technology plays a vital role in the teaching and learning process, especially in creating a comfortable learning environment. Secondary teachers have noted that integrating technology into classroom discussions can help maintain a conducive space, even with the barewall classroom policy in place. Elbow (pseudonym) discussed how technology can significantly enhance students' focus and engagement. He stated that tools like tablets, interactive software, and online resources capture students' attention and encourage participation. By using technology effectively, teachers can provide dynamic lessons that keep students motivated, helping them adapt to the more stripped-down classroom setting while still fostering a rich learning experience. He stated that:

“Kanunay nakong ginaisip nga ang silid-aralan kinahanglan nga angay para sa pagkat-on. Ikaduha, ang pag-apil sa teknolohiya sa pagtudlo aron mapalambo ang partisipasyon sa mga estudyante ug mahimong mas interaktibo ang pagkat-on. Sa katapusan, ang pagpahigayon og hands-on activities aron mapauswag ang aktibong pagkat-on ug mga kahanas sa kritikal nga paghunahuna.” (IDI_T2)

(I always have in mind that classroom should be conducive for learning. Second is, incorporating technology in teaching to enhance student engagement and make learning more interactive. Lastly, implementing hands-on activities for fostering active learning and critical thinking skills.)

Nails (pseudonym) shared that using technology is important for boosting student engagement in classroom discussions. She further explained that hands-on activities help students connect with each other. By incorporating technology, students can work together on projects and share their ideas more easily. Nails believes that this interaction makes learning more exciting and effective. As she stated, engaging activities allow students to participate fully and enjoy the learning process. As she stated:

“Usa ka epektibong pamaagi mao ang pag-apil sa hands-on activities ug interaktibong kasinatian sa pagkat-on. Ang laing pamaagi mao ang paggamit sa teknolohiya isip himan para sa partisipasyon.” (IDI_T5)

(One effective approach is to incorporate hands-on activities and interactive learning experience. Another method is to utilize technology as a tool for engagement.)

Mouth (pseudonym) provided more details on the types of technology that can be used in the classroom, like laptops, cellphones, and various reading materials. He stated that these tools can really help students in their learning. Laptops can be used for research and assignments, while cellphones can access educational apps and websites. Mouth believes that having different reading materials available can make lessons more interesting. He stated that:

“Mga alternatibong pamaagi gamit ang teknolohiya pinaagi sa cellphone, TV, ug laptop ingon man sa mga materyales sa pagbasa aron makatabang sa pagkat-on sa mga estudyante.” (FGD_T1)

(Alternative methods using technology through cellphone, TV and laptop as well as reading materials to help aid the learning of the students.)

Head (pseudonym) emphasized that integrating technology into classroom discussions can create a more stimulating and engaging learning environment for students. He expressed that using tools like videos, apps, and online quizzes keeps students interested in the lessons. Head believes that technology makes it easier for students to participate and share their ideas. This interactive approach helps them stay focused and motivated. As he what expressed:

“Aron makahimo og usa ka makapadasig ug makapaintereres nga palibot sa pagkat-on, nagtinguha ko nga mapaayo ug maapil ang mga litrato ug mga imahе sa akong PowerPoint presentation sa akong gi-discuss nga topiko.” (FGD_T2)

(To create a stimulating and engaging learning environment I tend to improve and incorporate pictures and images in my powerpoint presentation of my topic being discussed.)

Head (pseudonym) also agreed with Hair (pseudonym) that using interactive technology can greatly enhance students' learning experiences. He stated that tools like smart boards and educational games make lessons more engaging. Head believes that when students can interact with the technology, they become more involved in their learning. This hands-on approach helps them understand the material better. As she stated:

“Ang mga pamaagi nga akong giapil mao ang paggamit sa interaktibong teknolohiya sama sa digital displays ug mga educational apps nga makatabang sa mga estudyante aron mapalambo ang ilang kasinatian sa pagkat-on.” (FGD_T5)

(The methods I incorporated is that I used is that I incorporated interactive technology such as digital displays and educational apps which can help the students to enhance their learning experience.)

Establishing Clear Communication

The barewall classroom policy requires an effective communication process to be adopted. This approach aims at developing surroundings that are reduced to essentials and thus minimize the creation of clutter than can distract the students. Teachers can easily pass a message across when the class is less complicated and not full of many accessories. Such language and structure are very clear and specific, with help of pictures students always distinguish what they have to do. In general, extraneous information ensures people feel involved in the learning process and rarely have misunderstandings.

Clear communication is essential for effectively solving problems, and secondary teachers recognized its importance in implementing the barewall classroom policy. They organized meetings to inform both students and parents about the meaning of the policy and its rationale. Head (pseudonym) expressed that adhering to the policy can benefit everyone involved—students, parents, and teachers alike. He stated that when all parties understand the goals behind the policy, it fosters a sense of cooperation and support. Head believes that this shared understanding not only helps students adapt but also strengthens the overall school community, leading to a more positive learning environment for everyone. He stated that:

“Pinaagi sa pagsulti kanila nga kinahanglan nato sundon ang polisiya nga gipagawas sa DepEd ug siyempre, kini makatabang kanato nga mga magtutudlo kay dili kita makagasto og kwarta sa pagpalit og mga dekorasyon.” (IDI_T2)

(By telling them that we should follow the policy released by the DepEd and of course and it is beneficial to us teachers since we cannot spend money to purchase decorations.)

Just like Head (pseudonym), Leg (pseudonym) also discussed the importance of holding meetings to share information about the barewall classroom policy. He stated that these meetings are crucial for addressing any concerns and questions from students and parents. By providing a platform for open dialogue, Leg believes that everyone can better understand the policy's purpose and benefits. He emphasized that clear communication helps ease any worries and fosters cooperation among all parties. He stated that:

“Nakig-engage ko sa mga ginikanan ug estudyante sa pakig-istorya bahin sa barewall classroom policy pinaagi sa miting. Gisulbad nako ang ilang mga pangutana ug kabalaka nga nagpunting sa mga bentaha sa kini nga polisiya.” (IDI_T3)

(I engaged with parents and students in the conversation about barewall classroom policy through meeting. I addressed their questions and concerns emphasizing the advantages of this policy.)

Palm (pseudonym) emphasized how important it is to communicate with her colleagues when implementing the barewall classroom policy. As she stated, working together and sharing ideas makes the process easier for everyone.

She believes that clear communication helps teachers support each other and stay on the same page. Belly feels that discussing challenges and solutions can lead to better outcomes for students. As she stated:

“Busa, nakigkomunikar ko sa mga kausaban sa sulod sa among mga silid-aralan. Sama sa akong giingon, importante ang pakig-istorya sa imong mga kauban aron maipatuman kini nga polisiya sa maayo nga paagi.” (IDI_T4)

(So, I did communicate the changes inside our classrooms. As I have said, it is important to speak with your colleagues to implement this policy well.)

Belly (pseudonym) also emphasized the importance of organizing meetings to share the positive impact of the barewall classroom policy with students and their parents. She stated that these meetings help everyone understand the benefits of the changes being made.

By explaining how the policy can improve focus and learning, she believes parents and students will feel more supportive. Belly feels that open communication builds trust and encourages cooperation. She stated that:

“Pinaagi sa pag-organisar sa miting uban sa mga estudyante ug sa ilang tagsa-tagsa nga mga ginikanan aron ipasabut ang polisiya ug ipakita ang positibong epekto niini sa mga estudyante.” (FGD_T4)

(By organizing the meeting with the students and with their respective parents to explain the policy as well as highlighting its positive impact to the students.)

Hair (pseudonym) shared how she explained the barewall classroom policy and its benefits to her students. She stated that she took time to discuss why the policy was important for their learning. Hair believes that when students understand the reasons behind the changes, they are more likely to accept them. She emphasized that the policy could help them focus better on class. She stated that:

“Pinaagi sa yano nga pagsabot kanila sa mga benepisyong epekto niini para sa mga estudyante ug para kanato, nga mga magtutudlo.”

(FGD_T5)

“By simply explaining to them the benefits and its impact for the students and for us, as teachers.”

Creating a Conducive Learning Space

Education requires people to be in a correct environment hence the need to develop an environment that favors learning. There is also a policy whereby classroom should have bare wall to ensure that students do not distract themselves with what is on the classroom walls. This in a way, leads to reduction if decorations because such an environment is conducive for learning as it is well organized.

This approach fosters output that involves the utilization of the surrounding instead of the material being taught to the students. In general, an easy-clean and classical classroom arrangement may foster the efficient learning environment.

A conducive learning space is essential for enhancing both the learning process and the overall experience of students. Secondary teachers are committed to ensuring that students can still engage effectively, even with a white and plain classroom setup. Finger (pseudonym) expressed her approach by creating a flexible learning space that addresses the diverse needs of her students.

As she stated, adapting the classroom environment allows for various learning styles and activities, helping every student feel included. By focusing on flexibility, she believes that the classroom can remain an effective place for learning, despite the challenges posed by the barewall policy. As she stated:

“Sumala sa akong giingon kaniadto, nagmugna ko og flexible nga pagkat-on nga magtagbo sa lain-laing mga pabor sa pagkat-on sa akong mga estudyante” (IDI_T3)

“As what I have said earlier, I created a flexible learning that will cater the different learning preferences of my students.”

Nails (pseudonym) talked about how important communication and creating a safe space are for helping students maintain their attention. She stated that when students feel comfortable and heard, they are more likely to focus on their lessons. By encouraging open dialogue, she believes that students can express their thoughts and ask questions freely. Nails emphasized that a supportive environment helps reduce distractions and keeps everyone engaged. She stated that:

“Ang pag-amuma sa bukas nga komunikasyon sa mga estudyante ug paghimog usa ka luwas nga lugar alang kanila aron ipahayag ang ilang mga hunahuna ug pagbati makatabang sa pagmintinar sa usa ka positibong atmospera sa klase pinaagi sa aktibong pagpaminaw sa mga kabalaka sa estudyante.” (IDI_T5)

(Fostering an open communication with students and creating a safe space for them to express their thoughts and feelings can help maintain a positive atmosphere in the classroom and by actively listening to student concern.)

Mouth (pseudonym) talked about how a good learning space should have well-ventilated walls and clean paint. He stated that fresh air helps students feel more awake and focused during lessons. Mouth believes that bright, clean walls make the classroom more inviting and pleasant to be in. He emphasized that a tidy environment could reduce distractions and improve concentration. He stated that:

“Ang pagseguro nga ang silid-aralan adunay maayong hangin nga makagawas pinaagi sa maayong pintura makahatag sa mga estudyante og angay nga palibot sa pagkat-on, ug pinaagi niini, ang mga magtutungha makapadayon sa kalimpyo sa silid-aralan pinaagi sa pagpunas sa dingding”. (FGD_T1)

“So, by ensuring the classroom has a well-ventilated wall to give students a conducive learning environment through nice paints and with that learners can maintain the cleanliness of the classroom by wiping the wall.”

Head (pseudonym) expressed the importance of having clear classroom rules, norms, and policies. He stated that decorations are not the only factor in helping students learn. Instead, having a structured environment with guidelines helps students understand what is expected of them. Head believes that rules create a sense of order, allowing everyone to focus better. He stated that:

“Para sa akoo, ang mga dekorasyon ug mga poster dili lamang usa ka paagi aron mapadayon ang usa ka positibong palibot, mahimo usab nato nga maghimo og usa ka suportado ug positibong palibot pinaagi sa pag-establisar og mga norma, mga lagda, ug mga polisiya sa klase.” (FGD_T2)

“For me, decorations and posters were not the mere method to maintain a positive environment, we can also create a supportive and positive environment by creating a classroom norms, rules and policy.”

Just like Nails (pseudonym), Belly (pseudonym) agreed on the importance of open communication with all students. She added that a conducive learning space can meet the different learning needs of each student. Belly believes that when students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts, they are more engaged in class. As he stated:

“Sa pag-establisar og bukas nga komunikasyon sa akong mga estudyante ingon man sa paghimo sa classroom nga usa ka angay nga lugar para sa tanang klase sa estudyante.” (FGD_T4)

“By having open communication with my students as well as making the classroom a conducive space for all types of students.”

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of teachers and students in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy?

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 was presented in Table 6 and Table 7. Participants had their responses on what insights they can share with regards to the implementation of the barewall classroom policy. From the answers of the participants, eight major themes emerged: value cooperation, beneficial to students, conducive learning space, strong personality, clean classroom, embracing the change, better concentration and positive impact.

Table 6. *Insights of Students with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Value Cooperation	<p>“So, as a student, we have no choice but to cooperate with those in higher positions because we will eventually reach that position ourselves. We will be the ones in that position, and when we reach that kind of position, we will have the ability to change it. In addition, they have better goals and understanding beyond ours, so it’s better for us to cooperate.” (IDI_S1)</p> <p>“So, the advice that I can give to the students is to always trust the department of education because this is really for the benefit of everyone. This policy would not have been implemented if they did not carefully consider the majority. So, I am sure that they really see the many advantages that can come from this, many students and teachers can benefit from this. Well, it is really a big help to us.” (IDI_S4)</p> <p>“I also believe that DEPED had undergone study thoroughly before this policy implemented. Therefore, I will obey the rule and make a part for change.” (FGD_S3)</p> <p>“Let us just embrace the policy. I believe that the authorize personnel or DEPED already conducted or investigated deeper analysis before implementing it. As a student, I will cooperate to it, and I know these things were crafted for our own good and development.” (FGD_S4)</p> <p>“I accept all rules to be implemented since it is for our own benefit.” (FGD_S5)</p>
Conducive Learning Space	<p>“I realized that I could focus more on class because I do not have any other distractions to pay attention to.” (FGD_S2)</p> <p>“I realized that our room can now be called as a place where you can learn peacefully. It is conducive and free from distractions.” (FGD_S3)</p> <p>“I realized that it made me feel comfortable that there were no colors, words, posters and quotes that can distract me while our teacher is discussing in front. Our classroom became conducive space for learning.” (FGD_S4)</p> <p>“I realized that it is actually better if the classrooms are kept barewall so that students will not be too distracted.” (FGD_S5)</p>
Clean Classroom	<p>“To strengthen this policy, I will just follow it with open arms since this is for the welfare of the students, teachers and the institution.” (IDI_S5)</p> <p>“Make sure that the classroom is clean at all times.” (FGD_S1)</p> <p>“To strengthen the implementation of the barewall classroom policy, my role is to maintain the cleanliness of the classroom to prevent it from looking messy and to make it look neat and organized.” (FGD_S2)</p> <p>“To strengthen the policy, as a student, we should cooperate and to make the classroom always clean. As we cooperate, this policy will be more valuable and appreciated by both teachers and students.” (FGD_S3)</p>
Better Concentration	<p>“For me, it made me more comfortable to the class as well as I can concentrate well to the discussions.” (IDI_S5)</p> <p>“Well, in a positive way, it really helps because there are fewer distractions like that.” (IDI_S2)</p> <p>“I can deeply connect and focus to the class. I can feel that I am comfortable and unbothered.” (FGD_S3)</p> <p>“This policy does not really affect me because I feel more comfortable removing the designs.” (FGD_S5)</p>

Value Cooperation

Value Cooperation is critical in a barewall classroom policy whereby learning environment is important and so devoid of any distractions. In such environment, students are expected to help their colleagues and work in groups thus promoting teamwork. Most of the time it aids in creating good rapport among the level peers since they work on providing solutions together. Since there are less distractions to the eyes, the students can focus goodly on group work thereby sharpening their teamwork abilities. Finally, a barewall classroom creates unity and gives cooperation a significant value in the learning environment.

During the interview, it was highlighted that the insights of students are crucial for their cooperation in implementing the barewall classroom policy. Forehead (pseudonym) explained that cooperation among students is vital for successfully adapting to this new approach. She stated that when students work together and support one another, it creates a more positive atmosphere in the classroom. Forehead emphasized that understanding the purpose of the policy helps students feel more engaged and willing to cooperate. As she stated:

“So isip, uhm nga estudyante, wala natay laing mahimo kundi mo- cooperate sa atoang uhm, sa atoang kung kinsa tung taas nga naa sa position because paabot na lang ta kung kita na naa sa position, di kita, atong usabon but then sila man ang naa karun didtua sa position, and then kabalo man ta nga naa silay mas better na aim or naa silay mga goals and understanding nga beyond sa atoa, so mas better to cooperate na lang ta.” (IDI_S1)

(So, as a student, we have no choice but to cooperate with those in higher positions because we will eventually reach that position ourselves. We will be the ones in that position, and when we reach that kind of position, we will have the ability to change it. In

addition, they have better goals and understanding beyond ours, so it's better for us to cooperate.)

Hands (pseudonym) further detailed the value of the barewall classroom policy for students. He highlighted that when students see the benefits of this approach, they are more likely to trust the Department of Education in its implementation. Hands stated that understanding the purpose of the policy helps students feel confident in the changes being made. He believes that this trust can lead to a more supportive learning environment. As what he stated:

"The advice that I can give to the students no, is that to always trust the department of education because of this stuff, is para gyud sa kaayuhan sa tanan, yeah. Dili pud ni siya i-implement no of the policy kung wala gihuna huna sa pagkadaghan. So, sure jud ko nga kini nga policy nakita gyud nila nga daghan gyud ug kaayuhan ang mahimo ani, daghan jud ug ma benepisyo ang mga estudyante ani, ang mga teachers ani. Well, dako gyud kaayu siya ug tabang sa atoa." (IDI_S4)

(So, the advice that I can give to the students is to always trust the department of education because this is really for the benefit of everyone. This policy would not have been implemented if they did not carefully consider the majority. So, I am sure that they really see the many advantages that can come from this, many students and teachers can benefit from this. Well, it is really a big help to us.)

Ears (pseudonym) expressed the importance of believing in the Department of Education's reasons for implementing the barewall classroom policy. She stated that when students understand and trust the reasons behind the policy, they are more likely to support it. Ears emphasized that this belief helps create a positive attitude toward the changes in the classroom. She feels that trusting the department can lead to a smoother transition for everyone involved. She stated that:

"Nagtuo usab ako nga ang DEPED nag-agi sa husto nga pagtuon sa dili pa ipatuman kini nga polisiya. Busa, mosunod ako sa lagda ug maghimo og bahin alang sa kausaban." (FGD_S3)

(I also believe that DEPED had undergone study thoroughly before this policy implemented. Therefore, I will obey the rule and make a part for change.)

Cheeks (pseudonym) emphasized the value of cooperation with the Department of Education (DepEd) in implementing the barewall classroom policy. She stated that this policy is designed for the welfare of students, aiming to create a better learning environment. Cheeks believes that when everyone works together, it benefits all students. She highlighted that understanding the purpose of the policy helps build trust between students and teachers. She stated that:

"Atong dawaton lang ang polisiya. Nagtuo ko nga ang mga awtorisadong personnel o DEPED nagbuhat na og mas lawom nga pag-analisa o imbestigasyon sa wala pa kini ipatuman. Isip estudyante, makig-cooperate ko niini ug kabalo ko nga kini nga mga butang gihimo para sa atong kaayohan ug pag-uswag." (FGD_S4)

(Let us just embrace the policy. I believe that the authorize personnel or DEPED already conducted or investigated deeper analysis before implementing it. As a student, I will cooperate to it and I know these things were crafted for our own good and development.)

Conducive Learning Space

Education thrives in the right learning environment, and this is where the bare wall classroom policy comes in. If walls are empty their attention is fully on the lessons teachers are giving to them. Everything is simple and uncluttered, which leads to a clean and uncluttered learning environment being created. It also provides flexibility because it is quite easy for the teacher to switch between physical arrangement, or the items used in the class. In a nutshell, the bare wall policy can act as an effective strategy towards developing teaching and learning environment that is free and productive from various kinds of distractions.

During the interview, students shared their realizations regarding the implementation of the barewall classroom policy. They highlighted that this policy has helped create a more conducive learning space. Eyebrows (pseudonym) noted that the classroom is now free from distractions, allowing him to focus much better on his studies. He stated that without excessive decorations and visual clutter, he can concentrate on lessons and engage more fully in class activities. Eyebrows believes that this change has positively impacted his learning experience, making it easier to absorb information and participate in discussions. He stated that:

"Narealize nako na mas, na mas maka, mas maka focus ko sa klase kay wala man koy, wala man koy lain mapagtuonan pansin." (FGD_S2)

(I realized that I could focus more in class because I do not have any other distractions to pay attention to.)

Ears (pseudonym) shared her important realizations about the barewall classroom policy. She stated that the simple classroom setup helps her concentrate better on her lessons. Without distractions, she feels more focused during class discussions. Ears also noticed that this change encourages students to engage with the material more actively. She stated that:

"Nakat-on ko nga ang among silid karon mahimong tawgon nga usa ka lugar diin makakat-on ka nga malinawon. Kini angay ug gawason sa mga distraksyon." (FGD_S3)

(I realized that our room can now be called as a place where you can learn peacefully. It is conducive and free from distractions.)

Cheeks (pseudonym) shared a valuable insight about how the barewall classroom policy makes her feel comfortable. She noted that without decorations, she can focus better during class discussions. Cheeks expressed that a plain classroom helps reduce distractions, allowing her to pay more attention to the teacher. She believes this simple setup creates a calm environment for learning. She stated that:

“Nakat-on ko nga nakapahimutang kini kanako sa kahimtang nga komportable tungod kay walay mga kolor, mga pulong, mga poster, ug mga quote nga makadistract kanako samtang ang among magtutudlo nagdiscuss sa atubangan. Ang among silid-aralan nahimong angay nga espasyo para sa pagkat-on.” (FGD_S4)

(I realized that it made me feel comfortable that there were no colors, words, posters and quotes that can distract me while our teacher is discussing in front. Our classroom became conducive space for learning.)

Chin (pseudonym) emphasized how the barewall classroom helps improve students' concentration during discussions. She noted that without colorful decorations, it's easier for everyone to focus on what the teacher is saying. Chin believes that a simple environment reduces distractions, allowing students to engage more in the lessons. She feels this change has made a big difference in how well students pay attention.

“Nakat-on ko nga mas maayo diay kung ang mga silid-aralan kay walay mga dekorasyon aron ang mga estudyante dili kaayo madistract.” (FGD_S5)

(I realized that it is actually better if the classrooms are kept barewall so that students will not be too distracted.)

Clean Classroom

Clean classroom is also a nice theme that should be followed to bring a positive attitude towards learning. A bare wall classroom policy refers to the policy that only requires simple brackets on the walls thus no distractions for learners. It also enables students to direct most of their attention on what is taught in class and hardly get distracted by undue display of objects. A clean and simple environment can also enhance good order and study discipline in the case of pupils. In total, clutter less environment enhances learning as well as engages students in class.

A clean classroom plays a significant role in improving students' concentration. To support the implementation of the barewall classroom policy, students suggested that maintaining cleanliness is essential. They believe that a tidy environment helps minimize distractions, allowing them to focus better on lessons and discussions. By prioritizing cleanliness, students feel more comfortable and motivated to learn.

Nails (pseudonym) explained the importance of following the barewall classroom policy. He stated that adhering to the policy helps create a better learning environment for everyone. By removing distractions, students can focus more on their studies and participate actively in class. Nails believes that when everyone follows the policy, it shows respect for the learning process. He stated that:

“Aron mapalig-on kini nga polisiya, sundon ra nako kini nga abli ang mga bukton tungod kay para kini sa kaayohan sa mga estudyante, mga magtutudlo, ug sa institusyon.” (IDI_S5)

(To strengthen this policy, I will just follow it with open arms since this is for the welfare of the students, teachers and the institution.)

Nose (pseudonym) emphasized that students should always keep the classroom clean. He stated that a tidy classroom helps everyone focus better on their work. When the space is clean, it feels more inviting and comfortable for learning. Nose believes that by taking care of their environment, students show respect for their classroom and each other.

“Panatilihing malinis ang silid aralan.” (FGD_S1)

(Make sure that the classroom is clean at all times.)

Eyebrows (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of maintaining a clean classroom to support the barewall policy. As she stated, a clean space helps everyone focus better during lessons. She believes that when the classroom is tidy, it creates a more positive learning environment. Eyebrows emphasized that students should take responsibility for keeping their space clean. Overall, she feels that cleanliness is key to making the policy effective and beneficial for all students. As she stated:

“Para ma strengthen ang implementation of barewall classroom policy, ang akona is istay ang ka limpyo sa classroom para dili pud kaayo laay ug para hapsay pud tan awun.” (FGD_S2)

(To strengthen the implementation of the barewall classroom policy, my role is to maintain the cleanliness of the classroom to prevent it from looking messy and to make it look neat and organized.)

Ears (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of every student's cooperation in making the barewall classroom policy valuable. She stated that when all students work together, it enhances the learning environment for everyone. Ears believes that teamwork helps everyone adapt to the changes more smoothly. She noted that sharing responsibilities and supporting one another can make a big difference. She stated that:

“Aron mapalig-on ang polisiya, isip estudyante kinahanglan kita mag-cooperate ug siguruhon nga kanunay limpyo ang silid-aralan. Sa atong pag-cooperate, kini nga polisiya mahimong mas bilihon ug maapreciate sa parehas nga mga magtutudlo ug estudyante.”

(To strengthen the policy, as a student we should cooperate and to make the classroom always clean. As we cooperate, this policy will be more valuable and appreciated by both teachers and students.)

Better Concentration

The barewall classroom policy is about elimination of any traces that are likely to cause distraction to learners. The absence of too many accessories on the wall also helps student to focus on their study session. It helps to prevent students from being distracted by numerous logos, which are found in many other learning spaces. There are just not so many things to look at; they are able to focus on the teacher and the material being taught. In general, the classroom without any more or less is more conducive to concentration and brings benefits to the learning effect.

Concentration plays a crucial role in students' learning, and the barewall classroom policy significantly enhances this focus. By removing decorations and visual clutter, the policy helps create an environment where students can concentrate better during lessons. Students noted that with fewer distractions, they find it easier to engage with the material and participate in class discussions. This simplified setup allows them to pay more attention to the teacher and the content being taught.

Nails (pseudonym) talked about how the barewall classroom policy made him feel comfortable in the classroom. As he stated, the plain walls help him focus better without any distractions. He feels that a simple environment allows him to pay more attention to the lessons. Nails believes that this comfort helps him participate more in class discussions. As he stated:

“Para sa akoo, nakapahimo kini kanako nga mas komportable sa klase ug nakakoncentrar ko og maayo sa mga diskusyon.” (IDI_S5)

(For me, it made me more comfortable to the class as well as I can concentrate well to the discussions.)

Eyes (pseudonym) stressed the positive impact of the barewall classroom policy on her as a student. She stated that having fewer distractions helps her focus better during lessons. This clear environment makes it easier for her to engage with the teacher and understand the material. Eyes believes that the policy has improved her overall learning experience.

“Well, in positive way, nakatabang jud siya kay less distraction ing ana” (IDI_S2)

(Well, in a positive way, it really helps because there are fewer distractions like that.)

Ears (pseudonym) emphasized the connection and focus that the barewall classroom policy provided her. She stated that without decorations, she can concentrate more on the teacher and the lessons. This clear space helps her engage better with what is being taught. Ears believes that the policy allows her to connect more deeply with her classmates during discussions. She stated that:

“Makakonektar ko og maayo ug makafokus sa klase. Mabati nako nga komportable ko ug dili nabalaka.” (FGD_S3)

(I can deeply connect and focus to the class. I can feel that I am comfortable and unbothered.)

Chin (pseudonym) stressed the importance of removing decorations to lessen distractions in the classroom. She stated that a simple, bare environment helps students focus better on their lessons. Without colorful posters and items on the walls, it's easier to pay attention to the teacher. Chin believes this change allows everyone to engage more in class discussions. She stated that:

“Kini nga polisiya wala gyud makaapekto kanako tungod kay mabati nako nga mas komportable ko sa pagtangtang sa mga disenyo.” (FGD_S5)

(This policy does not really affect me because I feel more comfortable removing the designs.)

Table 7. Insights of Teachers with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Beneficial to Students	<p>“As a teacher, especially in the senior high school department, I perceived its impact on students’ engagement in several ways such as increased focus, enhanced participation and improved students’ creativity.” (IDI_T3)</p> <p>“For me, it is very positive. This policy has a huge impact on the learning of the learners as it will enforce the learners to focus on the discussions.” (FGD_T1)</p> <p>For me, barewall classroom policy has a positive impact not only for the students especially to the teachers as they will have enough time in preparing the lessons.” (FGD_T4)</p> <p>“For me, this policy is somewhat good and favors the teachers but for me as I make my classroom conducive, I put decorations that are essential to the students but now, I will not be able to do it since this policy has been implemented.” (FGD_T5)</p>
Strong Personality	<p>“The experience of implementing a barewall classroom policy as a teacher may shape a person by instilling values of discipline organization and prioritizing the educational needs of students. It can also highlight the importance of creating a conducive learning environment that supports student growth and development.” (IDI_T2)</p> <p>“It has shaped me into a more adaptable, empathetic, creative and resilient individual both personally and professionally. It</p>

	has reinforced my commitment to creating positive and supportive learning environments that empower students to thrive.” (IDI_T3)
	“My experience as a teacher with the barewall classroom policy has taught me valuable lessons about compassion, resilience and the power of positive reinforcement in shaping young minds.” (IDI_T5)
	“I learn to appreciate the things around me even if its bare and also I learn to be open minded and flexible to changes.” (FGD_T4)
Embracing the Change	“The only suggestion I have to other teachers, is just embrace the change.” (IDI_T3)
	“So, I would suggest that they should have an open heart and mind. As I have said, we have to be open to certain changes. I believe that this implementation would be beneficial to our students, and I trust the DepEd with its decision.” (IDI_T4)
	“Just follow what is being implemented because in the end, we will be the ones who will gain from this policy.” (FGD_T3)
	“The suggestions I have for other teachers is that, embrace the change, implement with the policy with open arms and make your best in teaching the students.” (FGD_T5)
Positive Impact	“Nice one. But it is essential for educators to strike a balance between creating a visually appealing space and ensuring that it does not overwhelm or distract students from their learning objectives.” (IDI_T2)
	I believe that the barewall classroom policy can be beneficial for promoting focus and engagement in students.” (IDI_T5)
	“For me, barewall classroom policy has a positive impact not only for the students especially to the teachers as they will have enough time in preparing the lessons.” FGD_T4)
	“For me, this policy is somewhat good and favors the teachers but for me as I make my classroom conducive, I put decorations that are essential to the students but now, I will not be able to do it since this policy has been implemented.” (FGD_T5)

Beneficial to Students

The barewall classroom policy can be advantageous for students in as much as it develops a distinct learning environment. This means that students are likely to have an easier time focusing on what they are taught as well as the various exercises they are taught. This makes it easy for them to interact more with what is being taught in class than if they were under a lot of stress. Thus, there are premises free from mess and clutter; this is useful because it makes students feel more relaxed. In general, it can benefit their learning experience and improve the outcome in their class.

Participants in the interview discussed various benefits of the barewall classroom policy for students. They highlighted how this approach fosters a more focused learning environment by minimizing distractions, allowing students to engage more deeply with their studies. Additionally, participants shared strategies for making the policy impactful, such as incorporating interactive learning activities and encouraging student creativity in decorating their own spaces within the guidelines. This not only enhances student ownership of their environment but also strengthens the bond between teachers and students, promoting a collaborative atmosphere that supports academic success.

Finger (pseudonym) shared how the barewall classroom policy helps students stay engaged and focused. She noted that without distractions, students can pay better attention in class. This clear space allows them to concentrate on their work more easily. Finger also mentioned that students feel more involved in their learning. She stated that:

“Isip magtutudlo, labi na sa senior high school department, akong nakita ang epekto niini sa pag-apil sa mga estudyante sa daghang paagi sama sa pagtaas sa konsentrasyon, pagpalambo sa partisipasyon, ug pagpaayo sa pagka-malikhain sa mga estudyante.” (IDI_T3)

(As a teacher, especially in the senior high school department I perceived its impact on student engagement in several ways such as increased focus, enhanced participation and improved students’ creativity.)

Mouth (pseudonym) emphasized the big impact the barewall classroom policy has on student learning. He explained that with fewer distractions, students can really focus on discussions. This helps them understand the material better and participate more actively. Mouth believes that a clear environment makes learning easier for everyone. He stated that:

“Para sa akoo, kuni nga positibo kaayo. Ang kuni nga polisiya adunay dakong epekto sa pagkat-on sa mga estudyante tungod kay mapugos niini ang mga estudyante nga magpokus sa mga diskusyon.” (FGD_T1)

(For me, it is very positive. This policy has a huge impact on the learning of the learners as it will enforce the learners to focus on the discussions.)

Belly (pseudonym) highlighted how the barewall classroom policy benefits both students and teachers. She noted that students are more focused, which makes teaching easier. With fewer distractions, teachers can present lessons more effectively. Belly also mentioned that this clear space encourages better communication in the classroom. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo, ang barewall classroom policy adunay positibong epekto dili lamang para sa mga estudyante kundi labi na sa mga magtutudlo kay makahatag kuni kanila og igo nga panahon sa pag-andam sa mga leksyon.” (FGD_T4)

(For me, barewall classroom policy has a positive impact not only for the students especially to the teachers as they will have enough time in preparing the lessons.)

Hair (pseudonym) talked about how she was told not to put decorations in the classroom. She explained that this made her feel disappointed because she wanted to make the space more inviting. Hair felt that a little decoration could help everyone feel more at home. However, she understood the need for focus in the learning environment. Despite this, she hopes there can be a balance between rules and creativity in the classroom. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo, kini nga polisiya medyo maayo ug pabor sa mga magtutudlo, apan alang kanako nga himoon nga angay ang akong silid-aralan, nagbutang ko og mga dekorasyon nga importante para sa mga estudyante. Apan karon, dili na nako kini mahimo tungod kay naipatuman na kini nga polisiya.” (FGD_T5)

(For me, this policy is somewhat good and favors the teachers but for me as I make my classroom conducive, I put decorations that are essential to the students but now, I will not be able to do it since this policy has been implemented.)

Strong Personality

A definite policy in a barewall classroom policy requires the teacher to have a strong personality so that the class is very disciplined and thereby very effective in carrying out the teaching-learning process. When the walls are empty and no other object interrupts the student’s focus, this will create the best study environment. This approach makes teachers reinforce their personality and appeal to the students as well as the community they represent. It also promotes the use of ideas in trying to teach the students because different teachers come with different styles of teaching. In total, Machiavellianism of personality increases and, together with an uncomplicated environment in the classroom, the process of education is promoted.

Participants noted that the barewall classroom policy helped teachers develop stronger personalities, even with the removal of decorations. Elbow (pseudonym) spoke about how this shift forced teachers to engage students in new ways, relying more on their teaching styles and interactions. Without visual distractions, educators became more creative in delivering lessons, using their voices and presence to capture attention. Elbow emphasized that this change encouraged teachers to connect with students on a deeper level, fostering a more dynamic and interactive classroom atmosphere. He stated that:

“Ang kasinatian sa pagpatuman sa barewall classroom policy isip magtutudlo mahimong makahulma sa usa ka tawo pinaagi sa pag-instilar sa mga bili sa disiplina, organisasyon, ug pag-prioritize sa mga pang-edukasyon nga panginahanglan sa mga estudyante. Mahimo usab kini magpasiugda sa kahinungdanon sa paghimo og usa ka angay nga palibot sa pagkat-on nga nagsuporta sa pagtubo ug pag-uswag sa mga estudyante.” (IDI_T2)

(The experience of implementing a barewall classroom policy as a teacher may shape a person by instilling values of discipline organization and prioritizing the educational needs of students. It can also highlight the importance of creating a conducive learning environment that supports student growth and development.)

Finger (pseudonym) shared how the barewall classroom policy helped her become more adaptable, empathetic, creative, and resilient. She explained that working in a simpler environment challenged her to think differently about her teaching. This experience made her more understanding of her students' needs. Finger also mentioned that it renewed her commitment to teaching. She stated that:

“Kini nakahulma kanako ngadto sa usa ka mas adaptable, empathetic, malikhain, ug mapadayonon nga indibidwal sa personal ug propesyonal nga aspeto. Kini nakapadayon sa akong pagpaningkamot sa paghimo og positibo ug suportadong mga palibot sa pagkat-on nga naghatag gahum sa mga estudyante aron molambo.” (IDI_T3)

(It has shaped me into a more adaptable, empathetic, creative and resilient individual both personally and professionally. It has reinforced my commitment to creating positive and supportive learning environments that empower students to thrive.)

Nails (pseudonym) talked about how the barewall classroom policy made her more resilient and compassionate in her teaching. She explained that the simpler environment helped her focus on what really matters—her students. This experience taught her to be more understanding and patient with their struggles. Nails also mentioned that facing challenges in this setting strengthened her skills as a teacher. She stated that:

“Ang akong kasinatian isip magtutudlo sa barewall classroom policy nagtudlo kanako og mga bilihon nga leksyon bahin sa pagkahumanon, pagkamapadayonon, ug ang gahum sa positibong pagdasig sa paghulma sa mga batan-ong hunahuna.” (IDI_T5)

(My experience as a teacher with the barewall classroom policy has taught me valuable lessons about compassion, resilience and the power of positive reinforcement in shaping young minds.)

Belly (pseudonym) talked about how the barewall classroom policy taught her to appreciate the things around her. She mentioned that with fewer decorations, she noticed the little details in her classroom and her students. This helped her focus more on the relationships she built with them. Belly also said that she learned to value the simplicity of the learning environment. She stated that:

“Nakat-on ko nga pasalamatan ang mga butang nga naa sa akong palibot bisan pa man nga kini yano, ug nakakat-on usab ko nga magbukas sa hunahuna ug mahimong flexible sa mga kausaban.” (FGD_T4)

(I learn to appreciate the things around me even if its bare and also I learn to be open minded and flexible to changes.)

Embracing the Change

The concept developed surrounded the classroom policy on barewalls exemplifies the need for citizens to accept new learning environments. I think barewall classroom where there are few stickers or anything on the walls might help to focus student's attention on the work to be done and the ideas they want to come up with. It can boost creation and critical analysis because the students are encouraged to use their personal creations and learning displays. By implementing this policy educators can facilitate active learning environment and personal development. In general, it can be viewed an attempt to lean closer to a student-oriented system of education.

Change is inevitable and can happen at any time. Secondary teachers are finding ways to make the barewall classroom policy beneficial for both students and themselves. Finger (pseudonym) suggested that to truly accept the policy, teachers need to embrace it fully. She explained that this means looking for the positive aspects and adapting to the new environment. By doing so, teachers can create a more focused and engaging classroom, turning the challenge into an opportunity for growth and better learning. She stated that:

"Ang usa ra ka sugyot nga akong aduna para sa ubang mga magtutudlo mao ang pagdawat lang sa kausaban." (IDI_T3)

(The only suggestion I have to other teachers, is just embrace the change.)

Palm (pseudonym) suggested that accepting the barewall classroom policy starts with having an open mind about its positive effects. She explained that focusing on the benefits can help teachers and students adapt better. By seeing how the policy can create a clearer learning space, everyone can feel more engaged. Palm emphasized the importance of being willing to change and try new approaches. She stated that:

"Busa, akong sugyot nga kinahanglan sila magbukas og kasingkasing ug hunahuna. Sama sa akong giingon, kinahanglan kita magbukas sa pipila ka mga kausaban. Nagtuo ko nga kini nga pagpatuman mahimong mapuslanon para sa atong mga estudyante ug nagtuo ko sa DepEd sa ilang desisyon." (IDI_T4)

(So, I would suggest that they should have an open heart and mind. As I have said, we have to be open to certain changes. I believe that this implementation would be beneficial to our students and I trust the DepEd with its decision.)

Leg (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of following the barewall classroom policy. She explained that sticking to the rules can help create a better learning environment for everyone. Leg pointed out that teachers can also benefit from this policy by finding new ways to engage students. With fewer distractions, lessons can be more focused and effective. She stated that:

"Sunda lang ang gipangpatuman kay sa katapusan, kita ang makapahimulos niining polisiya." (FGD_T3)

(Just follow what is being implemented because in the end, we will be the ones who will gain from this policy.)

Hair (pseudonym) suggested that it's important to welcome the barewall classroom policy with open arms because it can improve focus in the classroom. She explained that when the environment is simple, students can pay more attention to their lessons. This positive change can help everyone learn better and feel more involved. Hair emphasized that accepting the policy can make a real difference in how students engage with their studies. She stated that:

"Ang mga sugyot nga akong adunay para sa ubang mga magtutudlo mao ang, pagdawat sa kausaban, ipatuman ang polisiya nga abli ang mga buktion, ug buhata ang imong labing maayo sa pagtudlo sa mga estudyante." (FGD_T5)

(The suggestions I have for other teachers is that, embrace the change, implement with the policy with open arms and make your best in teaching the students.)

Positive Impact

This paper found that the implementation of the barewall classroom policy can result to positive outcomes for student learning experiences. When there are no objects on the walls, it prevents student's attention from being diverted, so they concentrate on their work. A plain environment fosters creativity you don't want to overcrowd the class with decorations because the students can imagine so much. This policy also helps implement a feeling of serenity that allows the students to easily get back to work.

Adapting to changes is crucial for progress, and secondary teachers recognize the need to be flexible to become effective educators. Elbow (pseudonym) discussed the importance of finding a balance in creating a classroom environment that is both conducive to learning and free from distractions. He emphasized that while a barewall classroom can help reduce visual clutter, it's also essential to ensure the space remains inviting and engaging for students. By thoughtfully managing this balance, teachers can foster a supportive atmosphere that encourages focus and enhances the learning experience. He stated that:

"Maayo kaayo. Apan importante alang sa mga magtutudlo nga makab-ot ang balanse tali sa paghimo og usa ka matahum nga espasyo ug pagsiguro nga dili kini makapadaghan o makadistract sa mga estudyante gikan sa ilang mga katuyoan sa pagkat-on." (IDI_T2)

(Nice one. But it is essential for educators to strike a balance between creating a visually appealing space and ensuring that it does not overwhelm or distract students from their learning objectives.)

Nails (pseudonym) emphasized that the barewall classroom policy helps boost student engagement and focus. She explained that with fewer decorations, students can pay more attention to their lessons. This clearer environment makes it easier for them to concentrate on what the teacher is saying. Nails also mentioned that students feel more involved in their learning when there are fewer distractions. She stated that:

“Nagtuho ko nga ang barewall classroom policy mahimong mapuslanon sa pag-promote sa konsentrasyon ug partisipasyon sa mga estudyante.” (IDI_T5)

(I believe that the barewall classroom policy can be beneficial for promoting focus and engagement in students.)

Belly (pseudonym) expressed the positive impact of the barewall classroom policy on both students and teachers. She stated that this policy helps students focus better on their work. With fewer distractions, teachers can deliver lessons more effectively. Belly also noted that it encourages stronger connections between students and teachers. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo, ang barewall classroom policy adunay positibong epekto dili lamang para sa mga estudyante kundi labi na sa mga magtutudlo kay makahatag kini kanila og igo nga panahon sa pag-andam sa mga leksyon.” (FGD_T4)

(For me, barewall classroom policy has a positive impact not only for the students especially to the teachers as they will have enough time in preparing the lessons.)

Hair (pseudonym) highlighted that the barewall classroom policy is essential for both students and teachers. She stated that it creates a simple environment where everyone can focus better. This policy helps students pay more attention to their lessons, improving their learning. For teachers, it allows them to teach without distractions, making their job easier. She stated that:

“Para sa akoo, kini nga polisiya medyo maayo ug pabor sa mga magtutudlo, apan alang kanako nga himoon nga angay para sa pagkat-on ang akong silid-aralan, nagbutang ko og mga dekorasyon nga importante para sa mga estudyante. Apan karon, dili na nako kini mahimo tungod kay naipatuman na kini nga polisiya.” (FGD_T5)

(For me, this policy is somewhat good and favors the teachers but for me as I make my classroom conducive, I put decorations that are essential to the students but now, I will not be able to do it since this policy has been implemented.)

Table 8. *Experiences of Teachers and Students with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy*

1. <i>What are the experiences of teachers and students in the implementation of barewall classroom policy?</i>	
<i>Students</i>	<i>Teachers</i>
Valuing Less Distraction	Following the Removal of Decorations
Stressing the Importance of Visual Stimulation	Enhancing Student Focus
Adhering to Classroom Changes	Viewing the Importance of Planning and Preparation
Enhancing Student Focus	Doing Careful Consideration

In the experiences of teachers and students with the barewall classroom policy, several unique themes emerge, highlighting both shared benefits and distinct challenges. A common perspective is the enhanced focus during classroom discussions; teachers note that the absence of decorations minimizes distractions, allowing students to concentrate better, while students appreciate the plain environment as less disruptive. However, the policy presents both positive and negative aspects for each group. While many students embraced the change, some struggled, particularly those who rely on visual stimuli for engagement. Teachers, on the other hand, faced challenges in removing decorations and adapting their materials, emphasizing the need for careful planning and preparation. They considered which resources would best support student learning while also considering diverse learning preferences. This dialogue between teachers and students reflects a collaborative effort to navigate the policy’s implications, showcasing a commitment to creating an effective learning environment despite the inherent difficulties of change.

Table 9. *Coping Mechanisms of Teachers and Students with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy*

2. <i>How do the teachers and students overcome such challenges regarding on the barewall classroom policy?</i>	
<i>Students</i>	<i>Teachers</i>
Embracing Acceptance	Participating Community Involvement
Being Adaptable to Changes	Ensuring Technology Integration
Adjusting Flexibly to Changes	Establishing Clear Communication
Understanding the Situation	Creating a Conducive Learning Space

In implementing the barewall classroom policy, both teachers and students have developed themes in their approaches to overcoming challenges. Students have generally accepted the policy, showing flexibility and a willingness to adapt to a classroom without decorations. They focus on understanding how to learn effectively in this simpler environment. Meanwhile, teachers have actively sought support from the community, including parents and students, to prepare classrooms that comply with the policy. Communication has been crucial, as teachers inform parents and students about the policy’s goals and benefits. They have also adopted various strategies

to maintain student engagement, such as using technology to enhance learning. Additionally, teachers prioritize creating a comfortable learning space by ensuring good ventilation, arranging chairs appropriately, and choosing a pleasant color scheme. Overall, despite their different perspectives, the collaborative efforts of both teachers and students have led to a successful teaching and learning process within the limits of the barewall classroom policy.

Table 10. *Insights of Teachers and Students with Regards to the Implementation of Barewall Classroom Policy*

3. <i>What are the insights of the teachers and students in the implementation of the barewall classroom policy?</i>	
<i>Students</i>	<i>Teachers</i>
Value Cooperation	Beneficial to Students
Conducive Learning Space	Strong Personality
Clean Classroom	Embrace the Change
Better Concentration	Positive Impact

In the implementation of the barewall classroom policy, both teachers and students have highlighted themes reflecting their differing perspectives. Students have stressed the importance of cooperation among their peers and teachers to achieve the policy's goals. They feel that the policy creates a better learning environment and helps them concentrate more during discussions, even without decorations. Additionally, they emphasize the need for maintaining classroom cleanliness to support the policy effectively. On the other hand, teachers have shared how the policy has made them more resilient, encouraging them to adapt to changes in their teaching practices. They believe that the policy ultimately benefits students by enhancing their learning experience and fostering greater engagement with classmates. Overall, the barewall classroom policy has positively impacted both students and teachers, improving the learning environment and promoting collaboration among everyone involved.

Conclusions

With all honesty, having this qualitative research study about the perspectives of teachers and students with regards to the implementation of the barewall classroom policy gave me an intriguing view of the Department of Education. However, there are times that I think that I would not benefit from digging deeper into the complexities of this policy. I wanted myself to become acquainted with them and help them share their experiences, ways, and ideas as to how they dealt with the implementation of the barewall classroom policy.

Furthermore, I pushed myself to continue and finish this qualitative study. This qualitative study would leave a mark on the person who read it and give this research the recognition that it deserves.

Indeed, this research led me to new learnings and realizations. This research allowed me to understand the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of the high school students and teachers with regards to the implementation of the barewall classroom policy. Their experiences made me realize how difficult it is to implement a policy that is way different from other school policies.

As a researcher and a future educator, I was proud to see them embrace the changes in the classroom despite the challenges they experienced. Those experiences will mold them into better people and professionals in the future.

References

- Agwu, S. N., & Ogochi, M. A. (2019). Assessing the effect of visual aids on secondary school students' Achievements in learning English language in Agbani education zone of Enugu state, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 4(10),1-2.
- Al-Mamary, Y. H. S. (2022). Why do students adopt and use learning management systems? Insights from Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Information Management Data Insights*, 2(2), Article 100088
- Akram M., Shah A., Rauf A., (2018). Head Teachers' Instructional Leadership Practices and School Climate at Secondary Schools, *Journal of Arts and Social Sciences II* (V).
- Ahmed G, Tayyub M, Ismail R (2020) Effects of Classroom Environment for Improving Students' Learning at Secondary Level in Punjab Province, Pakistan. *Sci Academique*
- Anderson, L. (2018). Building Empathy, Strengthening Relationships: The Benefits of Multiage Classrooms for Young Children and Their Caregivers. *YC Young Children*, 73(3), 34-42. Doi:10.2307/26788978
- Anteza, T. K. (2020). Management of a Conducive Classroom Environment: A Meta synthesis <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/46ed/d6707b9ca7cef4ea6b3df694578cdea2c587.pdf>
- Arshad, M., Qamart, Z.A., Gulzar, F.H. (2018). Effects of Physical Facilities at Public Schools on Students' Achievement in Punjab, Pakistan *Global Social Sciences Review (GSSR)* URL: [http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2018\(III-IV\).07](http://dx.doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2018(III-IV).07) p-ISSN 2520-0348, e-ISSN 2616-793X DOI: 10.31703/gssr.2018(III-IV).07 Vol. III, No. IV (Fall 2018) Anuradha Sharma(2017) Classroom Environment: An Analytical Review of the Related Literature http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2017/july/364_69_FINAL%20MANUSCRIPT-

ANURADHA%20SHARMA%20RESEARCH%20PAPER%20Id-IJ60707783.pdf

Asino TI, Pulay A. Student perceptions on the role of the classroom environment on computer supported collaborative learning. *TechTrends*. 2019;63(2):179–183. Doi: 10.1007/s11528-018-0353-y. https://scholar.google.com/scholar_lookup?journal=Higher+Education&title=International+stus+experienceinAustralianhighereducation:Canwedobetterauthor=SArkoudisauthor=MDollingerauthor

Awan, NM., (2018) Comparative study of availability and quality of physical facilities in public and private schools in the Punjab. *Journal of Elementary Education* 28: 99-107. http://pu.edu.pk/images/journal/JEE/PDF/9_v28_1_18.pdf

Baafi, R. 2020. The impact of school learning environment on students' academic performance in senior high schools in the Greater Accra Region, Ghana https://ppk.elte.hu/dstore/document/777/Richard%20Kwabena%20Akrofi%20Baafi_%20summary_baafi.pdf

Balog, N. (2018). Impacts of the Learning Environment on Developer's Progress. Accessed 4/10/2019 From <https://www.codingdojo.com/blog/impacts-of-the-learning-nvironment>

Batrися, AN., Hermawan, CM., Ida, A., Nurzubari, I., Rosfiniani, O, Saepuloh, A. (2023). Classroom Meeting: A Strategy for Establishing A Positive Classroom Climate.

Beckers, R. (2019). Learning space design in higher education. In K. Fisher (Ed.), *The translational design of universities*. (pp. 194–175). BrillSense. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004391598_010

Berkeley Center for Teaching & Learning. (2019). *Incorporating Technology into Your Teaching*.

Bluyssen, P. M. (2017). Health, comfort and performance of children in classrooms: New Directions for research. *Indoor and Built Environment*, 26(8), 1040–1050. Doi: 10.1177/1420326X16661866 <https://dc.etsu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=5133&context=etd>

Calamba, et., al (2019). The Effects of Classroom Environment on Academic Performance of Grade 1 Pupils at NHC Elementary School <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcpjmra/article/view/1197>

Chalak, A. & Fallanz, R. (2019). Effect of Classroom Management and Strategies on Students' Achievement at Undergraduate Level. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly* 2019, Vol. 11, 81–98

Cheng, M., Barnes, G.P., Edwards, C., Valyrakis, M., Corduneanu, R., Koukou, M. (2023). Transition Models and How Students Experience Change

Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research: planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative Research* / John W. Creswell. — 4th ed.

Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among 5 traditions*. San Francisco, CA: Sage

Collie R., Granziera, H., Martin, A., Burns, E. (2020). Adaptability Among Science Teachers in Schools: A Multi-nation Examination of its Role In School Outcomes School of Education, University of New South Wales

Dabba, N. (2019) *Using Technology to Support Postsecondary Student Learning*. The Institute for Education Sciences.

DepEd (2023). Retrieved from <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2023/08/21/2290296/its-final-deped-requires-schools-remove-everything-classroom-walls>

Ezike, B.U., (2018) Classroom Environment And Academic Interest As Correlates Of Achievement In Senior Secondary School Chemistry In Ibadan South West Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria .*Global Journal Of Educational Research*. Vol. 17, 2018: PP.61-71. Accessed 20/10/19 <https://academicjournals.org/journal/ERR/article-references/B4E1C7162538>

Domeier, L. (2020). Beyond The Fancy Table: How Does Classroom Learning Space Design Affect Student Social and Emotional Well-Being? <https://open.library.ubc.ca/soa/cIRcle/collections/graduateresearch/42591/items/1.0392692>

Federation University (2018), *Principles of learning Environment*: Accessed 22/09/2019 from: <https://federation.edu.au/staff/learning-and-teaching/teachingpractice/development/principles-of-learning-environment>

Fraser, B. (2007). *Classroom Learning Environments* <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203824696-6/classroom-learning-environments-barry-fraser>

Gruppen, L., Irby, D. M., Durning, S. J., & Maggio, L. A. (2018). Interventions designed to Improve the learning environment in the health professions: a scoping review. *MedEdPublish*, 7(211), 211.

Gunawan and F. Ananda (2017). "The thermal comfort aspect of the study room of a public high school building in The District of Saber," *J. Inovteknopolbeng*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 98–103

Han, et., al (2019). Physical classroom environment affects students' Satisfaction: Attitude and quality as mediators. *Social Behavior*

- and Personality, 47(5), 1-10, <http://doi.org/10.2224/sbp/7961> <https://nemss.unl.edu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/22-Optimal-Classroom-Learning-Environment.pdf>
- Hansen, et., al (2018). The impact of dynamic lighting in classrooms. A review on methods. Lecture Notes of the Institute for Computer Sciences, Social-Informatics and Telecommunications Engineering, LNICST. Springer Verlag, pp. 479–489
- Hariyanto. (2021). Benefits Of Student Attention in The Implementation Of Learning. Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT), 12(3), 3616–3630. <https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v12i3.1642>
- Haverinen-Shaughnessy, et., al (2015). An assessment of indoor environmental quality in schools and its association with health and performance. Building and Environment, 93, 35-40. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2015.03.006>
- Heyne D, Gentle-Genitty C, Melvin GA, Keppens G, O’Toole C and McKay-Brown L (2024) Embracing change: From recalibration to radical overhaul for the Field of school attendance. Front. Educ. 8:1251223. Doi: 10.3389/educ.2023.1251223
- Hogan, J. (2022). The Impact Of Clean Schools On Student Success And Teacher Retention
- Hudson,G. (2022).How The Classroom Environment Can Help Improve Behavior
- Hurley, S. (2016). Building capacity: Head meets heart in Canada’s newest school Designs. Retrieved from <https://www.edcan.ca/articles/building-capacity/>
- Ibem, et., al (2017). A Study Of Students’ Perception Of The Learning Environment: Case Study Of Department Of Architecture, Covenant University, Ota Ogun STATE https://www.researchgate.net/publication/315353245_A_Study_Of_Students'_Perception_Of_The_Learning_Environment_Case_Study_Of_Department_Of_Architecture_Covenant_University_Ota_Ogun_State
- Indeed Editorial Team, (2023). What Is Preparation in Teaching and Why Is It Important?
- Isuku, E. J. (2018). Classroom Management and Problems Associated with it. In Olusegun Kolawole and Bashiru Lawal (Eds) A Handbook of Teaching Practice. Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan
- Jing, et., al (2019). Thermal comfort and energy-saving potential in university classrooms during the heating season <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778819308527>
- Jones, C., Nillas, L., (2022). Fostering a Respectful and Engaging Classroom Environment. John Wesley Powell Student Research Conference. 3. <https://digitalcommons.iwu.edu/jwprc/2022/edstudies/3>
- Judijanto, L., Novitasari, S. A., & Muhtadi, M. A. (2024, April 30). Performance Analysis of Inclusive Learning Support System and Adaptive Curriculum Development on Academic Success and Independence of Students with Disabilities in Central Java. West Science Social and Humanities Studies, 2(04), 588–598. <https://doi.org/10.58812/wsshs.v2i04.832>
- Kaya, N., & Epps, H. H. (2004). Relationship between color and emotion: A study of college students. College Student Journal, 38(3), 396-405.
- Kayha, E. (2019). Mismatch between classroom furniture and anthropometric measures of university students, Int. J. Ind. Ergon., vol. 74, p. 102864
- Kliever, T. J. (2022). Does furniture comfort impact learning? Examining students’ perceptions about classroom Furniture <https://dr.lib.iastate.edu/bitstreams/3436640b-b4aa-46e9-a726-6b4326dcc5d1/download>
- Krueger, J. (2018). Designing the 21st Century Classroom: 6 Top Considerations
- Kwok, A. (2018).Classroom management actions of beginning urban teachers. Urban Education, 2018. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085918795017>
- Lawu, et., al (2022). Strategic Planning for Information Systems and Information Technology Using a Model Approach: Enterprise Architecture, Ward And Peppard. Indonesian Journal Computer Science, 1(1). <https://www.doi.org/10.22303/csrid>.
- Lincoln, et, al (2011). Paradigmatic controversies, contradictions, and Emerging confluences, revisited. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), The Sage Handbook of qualitative research (pp. 97-128). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Macpherson, J. (2022). Get Messy: Embracing Change in the Classroom. <https://www.vai.org/article/get-messy-embracing-change-in-the-classroom/>
- Mark, F. (2017). Flexible Classroom Design And Its Effects On Student-Centered Teaching And Learning. School of Education and Leadership Student Capstone Projects. 6. https://digitalcommons.hamline.edu/hse_cp/6
- May, K. E., & Elder, A. D. (2018). Efficient, helpful, or distracting? A literature Review of media multitasking in relation to academic

performance. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*

Nzowa, G. & Ngussa, B. (2019). Correlation between classroom atmosphere and language Competency as academic achievement among Secondary Schools in Arusha District, Tanzania. *International Journal of Educational Policy Research and Review* Vol.6 (6), pp. 164-175 <https://www.journalissues.org/IJEPRR/https://doi.org/10.15739/IJEPRR.19.019>

Omae NS, Onderi H, Benard M (2017). Quality implications of learning infrastructure on performance in Secondary education: A small scale study of a county in Kenya. *European Journal of Education Studies* 3: 97-123.

Oruikor, G.J., Ewane, H.D., Durotoye, M.P. & Akomaye, C.U.(2023). The Impact Of Classroom Design On Student Learning: A Case Study Of Cameron Schools

Prathoshni, S. M., Priya, V. V., & Gayathri, R. (2018). Effect of teaching aids on student's academic Performance in professional courses. *Drug Invention Today*

Ramos, S.E. (2022). Conducive Learning Environment: Avenue in Coping Student's Struggle in the New Normal *IJRP* 2022, 101(1), 419-426; doi:10.47119/IJRP1001011520223217

Rands, M., & Gansemer-Topf, A. (2017). The room itself is active: How classroom design impacts student engagement. *Journal of Learning Spaces*, 6(1), 26–33.

Rashid, H. (2023). Impact Of Classroom Design On Student Learning <https://limbd.org/impact-of-classroom-design-on-student-learning/>

Ravelli, L. (2018). Towards a social-semiotic topography of learning spaces: Tools to connect use, users, and Meanings. In R.A. Ellis and P. Goodyear (Eds.), *Spaces of teaching and learning: Integrating perspectives On teaching and research* (pp. 63–80). Springer. <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9789811071546>

Rode, D. (2024). New Study Shows Too Many Classroom Decorations Can Overload a Child's Brain and Get in the Way of Learning

Rode, D. (2024). *Strategies for Teachers: The Power of Preparation and Planning*

Roebuck, G. M. (2020). *School Environment, Academic Performance and Student Wellness: Investigating How Social and Built Components of a School Environment Can Optimize Academic Performance While Protecting and Enhancing Students Physical and Mental Well-being*. Master's Dissertation. Vassar College, New York. Retrieved from <https://theccd.org/wpcontent/uploads/2020/06/Thesis-2020-School-Environment-Academic-Performance-and-Student-Wellness.pdf>

Stock, R., Lynam, S., & Cachia, M. (2018, January). Academic success: the role of mental toughness in predicting and creating success. *Higher Education Pedagogies*, 3(1), 429–433. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23752696.2018.1507623>

Swanson E. (2017). Can we have it all? A review of the impacts of school choice on racial integration. *Journal of School Choice*, 11, 507-526. Crossref Google Scholar

Suleman, Q. & Hussain, I. (2014) Effects of Classroom Physical Environment on the Academic Achievement Scores of Secondary School Students in Kohat Division, Pakistan. *International Journal of Learning and Development*. Vol 4, No 1

Tapia-Fonllem, et., al (2020). School Environments and Elementary School Children's Well-Being in North Western Mexico. *Frontiers in Psychology*. 11: 510.doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00510

Terada, Y. (2018). Dos and Don'ts of Classroom Decorations

Trappet, L. (2023). Creating a Culture of Positive Community Involvement in Education <https://www.socialpinpoint.com/the-impact-of-positive-community-involvement-on-education/>

Umar, A.M. (2017) The Effect of Classroom Environment on Achievement in English as a Foreign Language (EFL): A Case Study of Secondary School Students in Gezira State: Sudan. *World Journal of English Language* 7: 4. <http://www.sciedupress.com/journal/index.php/wjel/article/view/12768>

Usman, Y.D. and Madudili, C.G. (2019). Evaluation of the Effect of Learning Environment on Student's Academic Performance in Nigeria.

Voon, H. (2022). How to Fully Embrace Change in Education Despite its Challenges <https://www.frogasia.com/stories/how-to-fully-embrace-change-in-education-despite-its-challenges>

Walck-Shannon, E. M., Rowell, S. F., & Frey, R. F. (2021). To what extent do Study habits relate to performance? *CBE—Life Sciences Education*

Watts, T., Nguyen, T., Carr, C., Feagans, L.V. & Blair, C. (2022). Examining the Effects of Changes in Classroom Quality on Within-Child Changes in Achievement and Behavioral Outcomes <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9279005/>

Widiastuti, K., Susilo, MJ., & Nurfinaputri, HS. (2020). How classroom design impacts for student learning comfort: Architect perspective on designing classrooms

Yang, et., al (2013). A study on student perceptions of higher education classrooms: Impact of classroom attributes on student satisfaction and performance. *Building and Environment*, 70, 171-188. <http://dx.doi.org.10.1016/j.buildenv.2013.08.030>

Ziwira, E. (2015). Creating a conducive learning environment <https://www.herald.co.zw/creating-a-conducive-learning-environment/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Trixie M. Villanueva

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Evelyn G. Erellana, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines